

D 6.2 Report on supplementary trainer guide and new training materials on RE/RI

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Author(s)/Editor(s)	Daniel Pizzolato, Kadri Simm, Erika Löfström, Anu Tammeleht, Josephina Antoniou
Contributor(s)	Giulia Inguaggiato, Signe Mezinska, Mari-Liisa Parder
Reviewer(s)	Carole Chapin, Vivian Mbanya, Rosemarie Bernabe
Approved by	Rosemarie Bernabe

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BEYOND Consortium

	ROLE	NAME	Acronym	Country
1.	Coordinator	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	European Network of Research Ethics Committees	EUREC	Belgium
3.	Partner	French Office for Research Integrity	OFIS	France
4.	Partner	French Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment	INRAE	France
5.	Partner	Oslo Metropolitan University	OsloMet	Norway
6.	Partner	Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK	TENK	Finland
7.	Partner	University of Central Lancashire-Cyprus	UCLanCY	Cyprus
8.	Partner	University of Helsinki	UH	Finland
9.	Partner	University of Humanistic Studies	UHS	The Netherlands
10.	Partner	University of Latvia	UL	Latvia
11.	Partner	University of Tartu	UTARTU	Estonia
12.	Partner	Stichting VUMC / The Embassy of Good Science	VUMC	The Netherlands
13.	AP	Trilateral Research LTD	TRI	UK
14.	AP	Heriot-Watt University	HWU	SCT

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1 Introduction

1.1 Abbreviations

RI	Research integrity
RE	Research ethics
RM	Research misconduct
FFP	Fabrication, falsification, plagiarism
QRPs	Questionable research practices
EC	European Commission

1.2 About BEYOND

BEYOND is a research project that aims to promote research ethics and integrity (RE/RI) and prevent research misconduct (RM) by adopting a complex ecosystemic perspective on the issue. The project will explore the existing literature on behavioural ethics and moral psychology, as well as the socio-economic consequences of research misconduct, and engage all involved stakeholders in public consultation. To guide and equip all stakeholders in the research ecosystem, BEYOND will utilise this knowledge to develop psychologically informed contextual interventions and methodologies to measure the impact of RE/RI training materials, a best practice manual and guidelines, and new training materials and tools. The project will mobilise all stakeholders involved in the consortium and the stakeholder advisory board to ensure widespread dissemination of results and facilitate their institutional uptake and embedding. By reinforcing efforts to promote adherence to the highest standards of research ethics and integrity, BEYOND aims to contribute to public trust in science and support the development of a strong research culture that is conducive to ethical research practices.

The project aims to explore and advance individual and institutional responsibilities in promoting RE/RI and preventing RM. To achieve this goal, the consortium will develop measures that are co-created, needs- and case-based, streamlined, and based on best practices. These measures will be designed to engage, advise, and equip research-related stakeholders through guidance and educational instruments. By doing so, the project aims to contribute to the development of a research culture that is conducive to ethical and rigorous research practices and that fosters public trust in science.

1.3 About this deliverable

This deliverable reports on the development of 1) a supplementary trainer guide based on the training materials created during previous EU-funded project focusing on research ethics and integrity and 2) new training material focusing on promoting research ethics and integrity. New training materials and tools will be based findings of BEYOND, especially on hitherto neglected topics such as mentoring, supervision and leadership.

The BEYOND Trainer Guide is a comprehensive resource designed for educators to promote integrity and ethical behaviour in research by teaching responsible conduct of research (RCR). It offers a detailed framework with practical tools and strategies for trainers to engage researchers in discussions, activities, and case studies, fostering deep understanding of ethical issues throughout the research process. The guide emphasizes critical thinking, ethical decision-making, and accountability, providing trainers with adaptable resources to effectively design and deliver impactful sessions tailored to various audiences, including students, early-career researchers, and experienced professionals.

The training material developed by the project will focus on two specific target groups, each with their own set of RE and RI topics. Materials on responsible mentoring, supervision and leadership are prepared for *senior researchers and managers*. Materials for the second target group – *junior and early career researchers* – are developed based on a gamification approach and focusing on topics identified during the earlier phases of BEYOND.

2 Background

The development of the trainer guide and the new training materials is based on the work reported in D 6.1. D6.1 reports on mapping the training material developed by previous EU-funded initiatives with the aim of presenting them to help trainers and educators to create their own trainings. BEYOND mapping aimed to understand the state of the art of training materials regarding their utilisation of insights from behavioural research and moral psychology in ethics education. The BEYOND project aims to develop a trainer guide that distils key insights from empirical and behavioural research on effective RE/RI education. This guide will supplement the materials and tools reviewed in D6.1, providing practical guidance for teaching RE/RI to different target groups, such as students, early career researchers, and seasoned researchers. The trainer guide includes materials coming from the following projects: PRINTEGER, ENERI, RID-SSISS, EnTIRE, VIRT2UE, Path2Integrity, INTEGRITY, BRIDGE and ROSiE.

The development of new training material is also based on D6.1. Recent advancements in research ethics and integrity (RE/RI) training materials emphasize critical thinking, moral development, and dialogical skills. Pedagogical approaches include constructivism and virtue ethics, using methods like storytelling, role-play, and reflection. Training is tailored to different career stages, covering topics such as responsible research practices, open science, and integrity issues. Notably, VIRT2UE offers a comprehensive trainer guide, while other programs provide less detailed instructions. However, there are gaps in addressing external factors influencing research practices, mentoring and supervision, publication pressure, and broader issues like diversity, inclusion, and AI in research. Additionally, training on social, financial, and environmental impacts is lacking.

3 Devise a trainer guide to enhance training materials and tools developed by related projects (EUREC)

The BEYOND Trainer Guide, developed based on insights from Deliverable D6.1, serves as a vital resource for educators aiming to instil a culture of integrity and ethical behaviour in research. It provides a comprehensive framework that equips trainers with both the knowledge and practical tools needed to teach responsible research practices effectively.

The guide features a structured approach for delivering engaging training sessions, incorporating discussions, activities, and case studies designed to foster deep engagement with ethical issues throughout all stages of research—from inception to dissemination and across various career stages. It also includes strategies for addressing ethical dilemmas that researchers may encounter, helping participants to enhance their critical thinking and decision-making skills.

Through the analysis of case studies and real-life scenarios, trainers can support researchers in navigating complex ethical challenges and making decisions that align with ethical standards and best practices. The guide promotes a culture of accountability and integrity, encouraging researchers to uphold ethical principles in their research activities and interactions with colleagues, participants, and the broader academic community.

Since its initial version, the guide has undergone continuous internal reviews, culminating in Version 0.3. This version was refined during an online workshop on June 19, 2024, with participation from WP6 members (facilitating the workshop), BEYOND SAB members (5 participants), and training material developers (12 participants). The workshop aimed to ensure that the trainer guide is aligned with and complements existing materials and tools. The contributors to this workshop are fully acknowledged in the guide.

The insights from this workshop informed the development of Version 0.4, which was then sent to workshop participants for further feedback. The attached version at the end of this deliverable is Version 1.0, which will be piloted during the third year of the project. The guide will be refined over the course of the project in light of experiences from the pilot tests in T6.4. Additionally, in collaboration with UCLan, an introductory video has been created to present the trainer guide to a broader audience. The video can be found on the BEYOND YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LWjoBVI7raY>.

4 Development of new training materials and tools on RE/RI

4.1 Training materials for supervisors and senior researchers (UH)

This material targets senior researchers who mentor, supervise and lead others. It includes training materials on responsible mentoring, supervision and leadership for senior researchers and research managers to facilitate the implementation of the best practices and guidelines. The training activities can be integrated into the ENERI Classroom and the Embassy of Good Science. From an 'orchard' perspective (that is, recognizing the role of the research community on maintaining high standards of RE/RI) it is crucial for leaders to understand that the way the community perceives fairness and justice may influence the culture of integrity. It is not only the guidelines and procedures that are necessary for fairness and integrity, but the role-modelling and standards set by the REI leaders. This is why we have developed reflective materials drawing on documented knowledge about the learning of RE/RI and facilitation of RE/RI learning, and providing models on how to constructively approach RE/RI challenges. Leaders, including supervisors and mentors, are role models for others, and the ways in which they handle RE/RI issues in the research community signals common expectations.

Supervisor development is supported through Collaborative learning and connecting content to cases. Prior research has shown that peer support groups, and collaborative reflection on own and others' practises are fruitful in developing supervision as pedagogy (Wichmann-Hansen et al., 2020; Wittek et al., 2023). Peer learning among supervisors has also been reported in e.g., Alebaikan et al., 2023). Training with a practical approach, and the use of cases have been documented to influence supervisor development positively (Jara, 2021; Wichmann-Hansen et al., 2020).

The development of the supervisors' material has proceeded in two phases.

In phase 1 national RE/RI surveys were analyzed (Finland, Estonia, Norway, France and the Netherlands) and this analysis fed into topic identification relevant for supervisors' training. The article is forthcoming.

The following topics for supervisors' REI training were identified:

- Help manage pressures and stress (at workplace/ related to studies and research).
- Openly discuss misconduct and QRPs (initiate such discussions).
- Share common values, beliefs, practices and importance of RE/RI.
- Show that support is available – guidelines, training, RI advisors.
- Promote RRP by being a role-model by showing commitment to best practices/guidelines.
- Being a role-model means showing your own values, beliefs, practices, but also fair and open decision-making.
- Address problems and misconduct in a fair and adequate way.
- Acknowledge power-relations in supervisory relationships.
- Learn how to balance support and learner autonomy.
- Consciously work on bringing up the next generation of REI leaders.
- In your team work on decreasing fear and increasing trust by openly discussing also difficult topics, leaving space for mistakes and disagreements.
- In your community fight against harassment and bullying.
- If you reach your limit, seek for help! Learn how to deal with emotional burden.

In phase 2 a training format was designed. Relying on strategies that have proven effective in REI training (case-based approach and collaboration) and integrating knowledge-building theory (Scardamalia & Bereiter, 2006) and the theory of the zone of proximal development (Vygotsky, 1980; see Tammeleht et al., 2022 <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40979-022-00102-3>) a training format was designed. We propose applying f2f training with posters, see section 5.2.

The training format includes 6 steps discussed in a group (colleagues, team-members, etc.) – either presented as a poster or a slide-deck. The steps are:

1. Getting to know the REI leadership framework (from Tammeleht et al., submitted) and taking the role of such a leader;
2. Reading the case. The case has a mentor-mentee situation and a dilemma for the leader/supervisor to deal with;
3. Identifying the ethical principles (e.g., Kitchener, 2000) that may be at stake in this case;
4. Using the ethical analysis (based on Mustajoki & Mustajoki, 2017) to solve the situation;
5. Analyzing which ethical approaches (consequentialist, rule-based or virtue-based) the possible courses of action follow; and

6. Reflecting back at the REI leadership framework – the group discusses which REI leadership principles would contribute to solving this case and reflect if they displayed any of the principles.

The cases can cover the topics identified in Phase 1 of the development work (see list above). The tasks have been proven to be effective in developing REI leadership competencies (see Tammeleht et al., 2022) and the improved REI leadership framework will be published in the forthcoming article. A QR code can be used to refer to the ENERI Classroom or Embassy of Good Science webpage.

Even though the content has been tested, poster format is novel and still needs to be tested, especially to provide instruction to facilitators. We believe the set-up of guiding activities, that is, identifying ethical principles and ethical approaches, conducting ethical analysis and applying the new REI leadership framework, support the collaborative case-based training format.

The activities and their structure are meant to support the following learning outcomes:

After the training participants

- understand what elements contribute to a culture of integrity in research communities
- are aware of both the implicit and explicit ways in which supervisors and mentors influence the learning processes of their supervisees/mentees and others working in the research community
- understand the role of and possess a command of practices that supervisors and mentors employ in establishing a culture of integrity
- develop and display competencies in ethical decision-making
- adopt the role of REI leader and display REI leadership competencies.

To facilitate the teaching and learning, a sample training kit will be compiled including:

- 1 (printed) poster (with replaceable alternative cases)
- A slide kit for facilitators (optional) (includes a digital poster)
- Report sheet (information to be collected during the piloting to provide unified feedback)

An example of the training material is given in section 5.2 of the deliverable and it has been uploaded on [Zenodo](#).

4.2 Training materials for early career researchers (UT)

As described in BEYOND literature review (D 1.1) there has been: *“a shift in RCR education from a focus on knowledge about ethical codes of conduct to the development of skills for ethical problem-solving (De Peuter & Conix, 2022). Case-based methodologies have emerged as a vital component of this shift, as they have proven to be more effective than traditional approaches in promoting deeper understanding and engagement with ethical issues (Todd et al., 2017). While case-based approaches have demonstrated significant effectiveness in enhancing ethical knowledge and decision-making (De Peuter & Conix, 2022; Watts, Medeiros, et al., 2016; Watts, Mulhearn, et al., 2016), case design and implementation greatly influence their efficacy.”*

Case-based methodologies use short case descriptions or vignettes with the aim of simulating what is happening in the real world and providing a space for participants to learn through positioning themselves in complex situations, taking on various roles and articulating the motives, reasons and principles involved. Materials can either be based on real-life events, modified real-life events or constructed as hypothetical scenarios. In this case, we used all of the above approaches.

The thorough literature review on behavioral ethics, moral psychology and case-based methodologies undertaken in BEYOND work package 1 identified a variety of recommendations that have been taken into account when developing training materials. We have combined the suggestion for the case length (cases needing to be realistic with low to moderate complexity) with our previous experiences with developing cases for facilitating discussion about ethics related matters¹ and chose shorter versions of the cases as noted by Medeiros et al (2017).

In terms of instructional effectiveness, we chose the methodology where possible solutions for the cases have been provided and students need to choose between these. While the methodology of providing only cases for students to resolve (without solutions) is well known, the method of offering a variety of solutions for the cases has been shown to foster intensive discussions in a short timeframe and make the peer disagreements explicit (Simm, 2020). Overall, the method relies on the premise that morality is social and intersubjective – moral decisions are decisions that we feel we can and need to justify to others.

The training materials – cases with solutions – are meant to be used as active learning methods with high interactivity (group work, group discussion) to facilitate learning. In terms of group and individual activities, the method combines having an individual component of the activity

¹ Centre for Ethics at University of Tartu has more than a decade of experience of developing case-based value-reflection educational games for a variety of target groups. Examples include materials for physicians, school teachers, pupils, researchers (<https://eetika.ee/en/node/154435>).

(choosing one's own solution) with group activity (discussing the case, solutions and coming to an agreement).

Development of the material

The material consists of ethical dilemmas which are developed in accordance with the methodology described by Parder et al. (2024).

- The narrative is described from the perspective of the protagonist – the protagonist must be someone that the trainees find easy to identify with.
- The actors and the basic relationships between them are described without going too much into detail, leaving thus room for trainees to fill the missing information with their own life experiences.
- The information about the motives of the actors has been kept to a minimum to give the trainees an opportunity to draw from their lived experiences.
- The temporal dimension of the narrative was kept limited – in some cases, some background information is given, but the pre-given choices were kept in one temporal moment.
- The dilemma and the pre-given solutions were balanced – the narrative was written from the neutral perspective and the pre-given solutions were morally acceptable from the perspective of at least one ethical theory.

The drafting of solutions was inspired by four relevant ethical theories: deontology, teleology, care ethics and virtue ethics. It has to be noted that the solutions are not in perfect accordance with the theories as the aim of this training methodology is not to teach ethical theories to trainees, but rather to provide realistic solutions to choose from.

Finally, the aim of the methodology is not to teach a “right” answer to the dilemma as dilemmas often involve conflicts between two or more valuable ethical principles, but to guide participants to carry out reasoning with emphasis on the skills of listening and discussing.

As a pedagogical method the feedback to cases will include articulation of important RE and RI values and principles. The core of the feedback will rely on ALLEA RE and RI values – reliability, honesty, respect, accountability. This will be complemented, as appropriate, by other research ethics values – non-maleficence, beneficence, justice, autonomy, openness and cooperation, freedom etc.

An example of the training material is given in section 5.3 of the deliverable.

RE and RI topics for early career researchers

The selection of training material topics for early career researchers was based on several considerations. Firstly, we took into account the findings of BEYOND WP1 that focused on mapping of REI issues. Secondly, the BEYOND project itself prescribed certain topics as relevant for junior/early-career researchers. Finally, we made special effort to address novel topics, that might have less training materials already developed.

1. Authorship issues – authorship criteria (in different disciplines), gift authorship etc.
2. Responsible whistleblowing – procedures and outcomes
3. Non-targeted use of research funding (i.e. use of research funds for other purposes than outlined in particular research project)
4. Participatory research and citizen science, possibly also third-party pressure, researcher as activist issues
5. AI - impact on research, responsible use of AI
6. Ethical supervision, mentoring (from the perspective of early career researchers)
7. Reintegration/rehabilitation of researchers
8. Gender aspects and RE and RI
9. Research in social media/internet

5 Attachments

5.1 BEYOND trainer guide

Research integrity
BEYOND bad apples

A European consortium

including three thematic networks

BEYOND Trainer guide

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1. Introduction

The BEYOND Trainer Guide is a solid resource for educators who want to cultivate a culture of integrity and ethical behaviour in research by fostering responsible conduct of research. It provides a detailed framework that gives trainers the knowledge and practical tools they need to teach researchers principles and practices of responsible conduct of research. At its core, the guide provides a structured approach to delivering sessions that engage participants in discussions, activities and case studies. These elements have been carefully crafted to stimulate deep engagement with the ethical dimensions inherent in every stage of the research process, from conception to dissemination of results, and at various career stages. The guide provides instructors with strategies to address ethical dilemmas that may arise during research, enhancing participants' critical thinking and ethical decision-making skills. By examining case studies and real-life scenarios, trainers can help researchers navigate complex ethical challenges and make principled decisions that are consistent with ethical standards and best practices. Trainers are provided with tools that promote a culture of accountability and integrity and encourage researchers to uphold ethical principles not only in their research endeavours, but also in their interactions with colleagues, participants, and the broader academic community.

The BEYOND Trainer Guide provides a research-based overview of state-of-the art in teaching research ethics and integrity. According to the extant knowledge base, case-based and collaborative teaching and learning activities, which make use of scaffolding techniques are the best ways to support learning in the context of research ethics and integrity. The BEYOND approach - 'it's not the apple, but the orchard' - reflects the same ideas. Integrity is upheld as a collaborative effort. This is why it is important that training also models the collaborative way. Cases have the capacity to open up discussion space for the complexities of integrity and ethics in research, again, guiding learners to think of the full complexity, not just individuals, but also other systemic levels, including meso and macro levels, that is organisation, research community, and national, international and global context. Scaffolding provides a technique acknowledging where the

individual or even a team or research community is at and designing the next steps to facilitate learning and development eventually leading to better alignment with the highest ethical and integrity standards. The point of departure is that there is always room for improvement, even in the strongest of research communities and the work starts with acknowledging status quo and identifying the next goals, which are within reach, irrespective of whether we envision the learning of individuals or communities. With these approaches; case-based and collaborative learning and scaffolding we believe training is well geared towards nurturing the orchard.

The BEYOND Trainer Guide introduces effectiveness measures to help trainers assess whether the training provided is impactful and beneficial. The versatile evaluation tools (developed in WP4) are designed to be applicable to various target groups and compatible with a variety of training activities and resources. Such evaluation measures are often absent in training resources, yet they provide trainers with a valuable mechanism to ensure how effectively training support learning. Understanding how training facilitates learning and development is necessary in the process of fostering and strengthening integrity in the research community. Provision of training is a necessary component of the overall building of a culture of integrity. Yet training, the effects of which are not monitored, falls short of its potential to mirror the change it contributes with to the research community. Therefore, in the orchard approach, learning and development provides important information about the readiness of the community to build a culture of integrity.

In essence, the guide serves as a comprehensive resource for educators seeking to support researchers and research communities with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to conduct research ethically and with integrity. Teaching research ethics and research integrity is incredibly important for several key reasons including fostering important skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and effective communication (ALLEA, 2023; Resnik & Shamoo, 2011; Science Europe, 2016). These skills are valuable not only for researchers but also for individuals in various professions and aspects of life.

This Trainer Guide provides guidance on how to effectively design teaching activities to foster responsible conduct of research to different target groups, such as students, early career researchers, experienced researchers and supervisors. It draws on prior research on teaching and learning research ethics and integrity and makes use of the vast training resources produced through selected EU-funded projects targeting ethics and integrity. It is a comprehensive resource equipped to

empower trainers in delivering impactful training sessions. Trainers can adapt and personalize it based on their specific audience, training context, and personal style. But its core purpose remains clear: to equip trainers with the knowledge, strategies, and resources needed to deliver engaging, informative, and ultimately impactful training sessions by bringing together research-based knowledge about research ethics and integrity teaching and learning, trainings produced in several EU-funded projects, and templates and activities for adapting materials to various target groups.

The BEYOND Trainer Guide goes beyond simply listing training materials; it adds value by explaining various pedagogical approaches that can be applied to enhance the use of different materials. It shows how learning taxonomies can be applied to create learning-focused training (as opposed to mere information transmission) irrespective of which materials produced in EU-funded projects that are implemented. We have structured the material according to target group, so that trainers can easily identify materials that are suitable for the target group they are training.

Additionally, the content is also structured according to the type of learning activities to support those trainers who wish to work using specific activities but may hesitate whether they are suitable for a particular target group, or simply would like to know more about the activity itself.

To summarise, the BEYOND approach is manifested in the Trainer Guide as:

- A proposal for a research-based approach to an ‘orchard pedagogy’
- Suggestions for measuring training effect to gain an indication of the preparedness of the research community to develop a culture of integrity

Facilitation for using existing RE/RI training resources by providing two alternative structures for trainers, including one, which addresses various actors in ‘the orchard’ through a career-level approach. We wish trainers and other readers, as well as learners taking part in trainings and learning activities utilising the resources referred to in the BEYOND Trainer Guide, a joyful journey through the orchard!

2. RCR education and training

2.1 The goals of RCR education

The ethical conduct of research is crucial for maintaining the integrity of science. [Responsible Conduct of Research](#) (RCR) advances scientific goals, fosters a collaborative research environment, and builds public trust in scientific advances that benefit society. Conversely, unethical research practises such as data fabrication and falsification lead to the dissemination of false hypotheses and unreliable data, which harms the search for valid knowledge. Similarly, plagiarism and harassment undermine respect and trust among researchers, while fraudulent or socially irresponsible research weakens public trust and support for science. [The goals of RCR training](#) include developing a culture of integrity in science and improving knowledge and awareness about the conduct of research.

RCR training and education should be continuous and extend beyond the academic programme throughout a scientist's career. This education can take place in a variety of contexts, such as seminars, workshops, conferences on research ethics and informal mentoring sessions, training courses and laboratory meetings where ethical behaviour and practises are discussed.

As described by van den Hoven and colleagues (2023), multiple factors influence research integrity (RI) training (learning objectives), RI learning (learning outcomes), and changes in RI behaviour (learning outcomes). Through these, it is possible to promote trustworthy science, responsible research practices, and high integrity/ethical standards. "Training effects" Can be conceptualised through the (intended) impacts of RI training on various performance levels, including individual, institutional, and societal levels (van den Hoven et al., 2023). Furthermore, the authors distinguish among intended training effects (for example changes in behaviour); training input and output (that is training focus/content and learners orientating themselves towards this content); outcomes (that is, learners change their behaviour); and training impact (manifestation of the outcome, such as decreases in misconduct).

[Effective education in research ethics and integrity aims to achieve several crucial goals.](#) Defining goals for teaching research integrity and research ethics is crucial to promote and foster responsible research practices and a trustworthy research ecosystem. The main goals to achieve in training RE/RI are related to promoting knowledge (in relation to responsible research practices, norms, and

guidelines), skills (in relation to ethical decision-making, problem solving and critical thinking), ‘theoretical’ attitude (in relation to what should be done to foster responsible research) and ‘practical’ behaviour (in relation to how researchers behave in their daily practice) (Kalichman & Plemmons, 2007).

2.2 Defining learning objectives: applying taxonomies of learning

Defining learning objectives serves as a cornerstone for creating successful and impactful learning environments. Learning objectives, that, is what is it that the learners should learn by taking part in the training, guides the choice of content, activities and assessment. Learning objectives can be defined by using taxonomies. Bloom's taxonomy categorizes educational goals into a hierarchical model, from simple recall of facts to complex evaluation and creation tasks. The SOLO (Structure of Observed Learning Outcomes) taxonomy, on the other hand, describes levels of increasing complexity in a learner's understanding of subjects, ranging from unistructural to extended abstract levels.

Learning is what the learner does but can be facilitated through what trainers do and of appropriate teaching activities (Biggs, 1999). The Taxonomy of Significant Learning (Fink, 2013) (sometimes also referred as the [Fink's taxonomy](#)) is not hierarchical in the same way as the other two, however, it builds on Blooms' taxonomy by including a long-forgotten affective component into the discussion, namely caring. It encourages to include into the learning objectives foundational knowledge, application, integration, a human dimension, caring, and learning to learn competencies (Fink, 2013) and this way offers a holistic approach to learning. However, since the existing material aligns with Bloom's and SOLO frameworks, this guide will primarily describe these two to ensure coherence and consistency in training delivery. Nevertheless, we encourage trainers to also consider the more affective type of learning objectives proposed in the Taxonomy of Significant Learning.

Bloom's taxonomy

Bloom's Taxonomy is a well-known educational framework that offers a methodical way to classify learning objectives according to cognitive difficulty (e.g., Adams, 2015). Bloom's

taxonomy is a hierarchical framework that uses cognitive complexity to classify learning objectives. Benjamin Bloom created it in the 1950s, and it is now a vital instrument in educational theory and practice. The taxonomy is divided into six stages: remembering, understanding, applying, analysing, evaluating, and creating. The levels are arranged from lower to higher order cognitive skills. Fundamentally, remembering entails recollecting words, information, and fundamental ideas. Understanding is more than just remembering concepts; it also involves understanding meanings. Applying necessitates applying knowledge to novel contexts or problem-solving. Analysing means dissecting data into its constituent elements and identifying connections between them. Making decisions based on standards and criteria is the process of evaluating. Creating involves coming up with original concepts and/or interpretations. The goal of applying Bloom's Taxonomy to training aims and results is to enhance comprehension by considering the knowledge, skills, and competencies that the specific training programmes were created to impart. The Remembering, Understanding, Applying, Analysing, Evaluating, and Creating domains of Bloom's Taxonomy each reflect a different cognitive process and the depth and complexity of learning.

Fig 1. Bloom's Taxonomy (taken from the Centre for teaching, Vanderbilt University. <https://cft.vanderbilt.edu/guides-sub-pages/blooms-taxonomy/>)

All taxonomic levels are relevant irrespective of the study or career level. However, the taxonomic levels may mean different things for different individuals. For example, application of knowledge may mean engaging with research designs, but senior researchers often use more complex designs than students still learning how to do research. Nevertheless, it is essential that the learning extends beyond remembering and understanding, and that the complexity of activities at all levels gradually grow as the individual gains experience, knowledge and confidence.

Remembering and understanding:

Here, the focus is on memorising key facts, concepts and theories relevant to the field of research and innovation. Understanding these foundational elements is critical to moving forward. For example, undergraduate students need to master the basic principles and terminology related to ethics and integrity to effectively navigate through more complex topics later. Similarly, individuals pursuing a PhD or who are new to academia need a solid understanding of basic concepts before they can conduct more in-depth analyses and applications, such as mastering the ethics of their own PhD research. Moreover, senior researchers may need to understand basic concepts of supervision and mentoring practices when it comes to supervise a team and PhD candidates.

Apply and analyse:

Learning should always be an active endeavour irrespective of career or studies applying and analysing knowledge. This is where the emphasis shifts to practical application and critical thinking. Early career researchers, junior professors and academics need competencies for applying ethics and integrity concepts to real-life scenarios in connection to conducting experiments, collecting data and critically analysing the results to gain meaningful insights. Through these activities, participants develop the skills necessary to contribute to the advancement of their field and address research questions with greater depth and sophistication. In terms of research ethics and integrity, this involves applying such knowledge and values to every step of the research.

Evaluate and Create:

The highest level in Bloom's Taxonomy involves evaluating existing knowledge and creating new knowledge. All researchers play a critical role in shaping the direction of research and innovation. They are responsible for assessing the validity and significance of research findings and identifying areas for further investigation and innovation. By synthesising existing knowledge and developing

new ideas, theories or methods, researchers develop their field forward and inspire the next generation of researchers and innovators. All RE/RI training should include components, which encourage learners to extend their thinking to evaluation and creation. In practice, this involves having such a robust knowledge base and values so that even when encountering new ethical dilemmas or being posed with a novel potentially integrity-threatening situation, they can rely on having the ‘tools’ to handle the situation.

SOLO Taxonomy

The *Structure of the Observed Learning Outcome*, or SOLO, is a way to set the learning outcomes according to their complexity. (Biggs, 1999; Biggs & Tang, 2007). This allows us to evaluate students' work based on its quality following the idea of increasing understanding of complexities: Initially, we learn one or a few aspects of the task (unistructural), then multiple aspects that are unrelated to each other (multistructural), then we learn how to integrate them into a whole (relational), and lastly, we can generalise that whole to still-untaught applications (extended abstract).

SOLO taxonomy level	General explanation (Biggs, 1999; Biggs & Tang, 2007)
Extended ABSTRACT (4)	The coherent whole is generalised or reconceptualised to a higher level of abstraction - the response goes beyond conceptualising; higher level of abstraction is present with application to new and broader domains. Displaying the ability to theorise, generate, generalise, hypothesise, create, or reflect.
Relational (3)	Relevant aspects are integrated into an overall coherent structure - ability to address the point and provide explanations, give details, and connect to the whole, giving relevant examples.
Multi-structural (2)	Several aspects have been understood, but not relating them to one another - ability to enumerate, describe, illustrate, sequence, select, combine, follow procedures, but struggle to make the connections between them or draw conclusions based on interrelations.
Unistructural (1)	Knowledge enables learner to identify, recognise, count, find, label, match, name, perform simple procedures. One relevant aspect is understood - dealing with terminology, meeting part of the task, defining concepts while some aspects still missing.
Pre-structural (0)	The issue is not approached in a meaningful way - repeating the words in the question/case/code; no understanding.

Fig 2. SOLO taxonomy (taken from Tammeleht & Lofström, 2023)

The SOLO taxonomy has been used to evaluate effectiveness of trainings as well as the development of ethical sensitivity and has been proven to be effective in the context of research ethics and integrity training (Löfström, 2012; Tammeleht & Löfström, 2023; Tammeleht, Löfström & Rodríguez-Triana, 2022; Tammeleht, Löfström & Rajando, 2024). The verbs emphasised in the descriptions below can be used as indicators of the appropriate levels in learning objectives.

Pre-structural level (0)

At the pre-structural level the learner fails to identify or approach topics in a meaningful way, but simply repeats the words in the question without understanding them.

Unistructural level (1)

At the unistructural level, the learner has sufficient knowledge to *identify, recognise, count, find, label, match, name, and follow simple procedures*. The learner identifies one relevant aspect displaying some familiarity with relevant concepts but failing to outline multiple dimensions of it. In the context of research ethics and integrity, this may mean identifying certain, perhaps common concepts, but having a limited view of them. For example, the learner may be able to identify some of the things that ought to be mentioned in an information letter to research participants but fails to understand all aspects of ensuring voluntary participation in research.

Multi-structural level (2)

At the multistructural level, the learner can *enumerate, describe, illustrate, list, sequence, select, combine, and follow procedures*, but struggles to make connections between concepts or draw conclusions based on interrelations. For example, the learner may understand that informed consent is necessary in research but fails to understand that this is so because of the need to respect people's autonomy and right to make decisions that concern themselves.

Relational level (3)

At the relational level, the learner displays an ability to address the most relevant aspects of the concept and provide explanations pointing out interrelations and providing examples demonstrating own reasoning. Corresponding action verbs include; *analyse, apply, argue, compare, contrast, critique, explain causes, relate and justify*. For example, the learner understands at least the main mechanisms and connections between FFP and the detrimental effects to science.

Extended abstract level (4)

At the extended abstract level, the coherent whole is generalised or re-conceptualised at a higher level of abstraction. The learner grasps a more abstract version of the concept and recognises other domains to which the concept might be applied by displaying the ability to *theorise, generate, generalise, hypothesise, create, formulate* and *reflect*. For example, the learner is able to use knowledge about ethical analysis and ethical principles to solve a novel integrity-related dilemma, which the learner recognises is affecting a research group, but to which the learner has not been exposed before.

The Taxonomy of Significant Learning

The taxonomy of Significant Learning or the Fink's taxonomy is non-hierarchical and helps trainers devise learning outcomes to support deep learning. No dimension is considered more important than the other and within the course various aspects should be present (Fink, 2013). Thus, this taxonomy provides an alternative frame for devising learning objectives for training. The fact that this taxonomy emphasises care and empathy makes it very suitable for training on ethics and integrity. The following is a short overview of the various dimensions (based on Fink, 2013):

Foundational knowledge

This dimension focuses on content knowledge and includes recalling and understanding of information and ideas.

Application

Here the learner demonstrates skills – they can be related to the use of knowledge or include skills necessary to interact in the subject, e.g. critical and creative thinking, decision-making, solving problems etc. For example, using the steps of ethical analysis to solve a situation involving an integrity-related challenge.

Integration

In this dimension the learner perceives connections between various ideas, disciplines, experiences. It includes relating various ideas to each other, comparing, contrasting ideas and examples and so on. For example, in solving an ethical issue, different ethical theoretical points of departure may lead to diverse actions and solutions. Recognising how for example a virtue ethical approach may

lead to a different solution than reasoning based on utilitarianism may be an expression of integration.

Human dimension

Learners learn with others, and they gain new understanding of themselves as well as others in the learning process. They recognise how people influence each other. Understanding how to respectfully work together for the greater good is an example of how the human dimension materialises positively in practice.

Caring

The caring dimension includes an affective stance and involves change in a learner. The learners start to see the reason to care about a topic, they gain new interests, feelings and values about the subject. Empathy and an ethics of care are values compatible with caring.

Learning to learn

In this dimension the learner understands that it is not only the outcome of learning that matters but also the process is important. This dimension includes guiding one’s learning for instance by inquiry, reflection and self-assessment. The role of reflection has been emphasised as a key activity in learning and individual development.

To illustrate how the taxonomies can be applied in creating learning objectives for training, we provide an example of an analysis of learning outcomes in RID-SSISS training material based on the three taxonomies (Table 1).

Level of training material	Learning outcomes	Bloom	SOLO	Fink
Foundational level	Raise awareness of ethical issues during the research process;	remember, understand	unistructural, multistructural, relational	foundational knowledge
	Practice utilising the codes of	understand, apply, analyse	relational, extended abstract	applicatipon, integration

	conduct, being familiar with central topics;			
	Learn together as a team, collaborate with peers.	evaluate	relational	human dimension, learning to learn, caring
Advanced level	Develop one's research ethics competencies by combining previous knowledge and implementing new tools;	understand, apply	unistructural, multistructural, relational	foundational knowledge, application, integration, learning to learn
	Identify ethical issues by determining which ethical principle (Kitchener, 1985) might be at stake;	analyse, evaluate	unistructural, multistructural, relational	application, integration
	Utilise the ethical analysis (Mustajoki & Mustajoki, 2017) steps to provide solutions to ethical dilemmas (in groups).	apply, analyse, evaluate, create	unistructural, multistructural, relational, extended abstract	foundational knowledge, application, integration, human dimension, caring, learning to learn
Leadership level	Develop research ethics competencies by	understand, apply	unistructural, multistructural, relational	foundational knowledge, application,

	combining previous knowledge and implementing new tools;			integration, learning to learn
	Identify which ethical principles (Kitchener, 1985) might be at stake in a case;	analyse, evaluate	unistructural, multistructural, relational	application, integration
	Utilise the ethical analysis steps (Mustajoki & Mustajoki, 2017) to provide solutions to ethical dilemmas;	apply, analyse, evaluate, create	unistructural, multistructural, relational, extended abstract	foundational knowledge, application, integration, human dimension, caring, learning to learn
	Implement different ethical approaches to the possible courses of action;	analyse, evaluate	unistructural, multistructural, relational	foundational knowledge, application, integration,
	Take the role of a REI leader and display (some) REI leadership competencies during their group work.	apply, analyse, evaluate, create	relational, extended abstract	human dimension, caring, learning to learn

Table 1: Example of an analysis of learning outcomes in RID-SSISS training material based on three taxonomies

The coordination between learning goals or objectives, the methods used for teaching and the activities chosen to support learning, as well as the assessment of the learning are referred to as constructive alignment (Biggs, 1996; 1999; Biggs & Tang, 2007). This means that the core components of a teaching should be geared towards the supporting the same aim; namely learning. Learning taxonomies are helpful not only in the designing learning goals for teaching, but also in devising appropriate targets of assessment.

2.3 Tools for evaluating training effectiveness

Evaluating training effectiveness to ensure training programs achieve their intended outcomes is crucial because it connects training investments to tangible results, ensuring that the effort put into developing and delivering training is worthwhile, and for pinpointing further development needs.

Effectiveness of research ethics and integrity (REI) training can be viewed through an established effectiveness framework (Kirkpatrick, 1959, Praslova, 2010), which identifies four outcome domains, namely:

1. reactions (participants' self-assessment),
2. learning (knowledge, content),
3. behaviour (acting in the research community),
4. results (e.g. institutional outcomes).

Evaluating development of ethical competencies should be done as a **system** to get a more holistic picture. To do this, one can combine **different forms of measurement**, such as self-assessment and facilitator feedback as well as attitudes and behaviour traits (in tasks that display REI competencies in research community, like research proposals, ethics sections of theses, articles, etc.). Furthermore, measurement could take place at different **time** points to gain insight into the learning process, learning outcome, and long-term implications, namely:

- during the training (learning process),
- right after the training – students' and facilitator's self-reports,
- later as part of another event or course where the display of REI competencies is expected (like RE section in theses and articles, research proposal, evaluation of RE situation in the department, etc.)

It is also important to consider **what to do with the results**, that is what kind of changes are necessary to improve teaching and/or the environment to build the culture of integrity.

Different tools can be used to collect various learning outputs and analysis instruments can be implemented to analyse the information that has been collected (Table 2) By analysis instruments we mean the taxonomies of learning and application of theoretical models, such as levels of reflection, ethical principles and so on (if data available are mainly in a qualitative format) or statistics and learning analytics (if the data are mainly in quantitative format).

Tool for collecting learning outputs	Details	Analysis instrument (see details in WP4.2)
ProLearning app	<i>ProLearning</i> : www.prolearning.realto.ch	learning analytics
Engagement app	<i>ForgetNot</i> (by EduLog): https://web.htk.tlu.ee/forgetnot	learning analytics
Self-Reflection Form/Compass	App under development, form (for copying and editing)	SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels, content criteria
Pre-post texts	Collect a short text (e.g. a response to a case or short essay) before the training and after the training	SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels, content criteria
Learning diaries	Ask learners keep a diary over a certain period, for each submission provide some guiding questions or topics	SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels, content criteria
Group reports	Ask groups working together to provide a (short) group report (or provide a template with points to work on)	SOLO taxonomy, content criteria
Group discussions	Monitor the group discussions to evaluate the level of understanding and	SOLO taxonomy, content criteria

	content discussed (scaffold as appropriate)	
Group dynamics	CoTrack application: https://www.cotrack.website/en/	learning analytics
Online learning platform	Make use of accumulated authentic learning outputs in the learning platform.	statistics, SOLO taxonomy, reflection scale, content criteria
Domain-specific/ domain-transcending measure	Use either of the two forms (WP4.2) measuring recognition and exemplifying of ethical issues.	statistics, SOLO taxonomy, content criteria
Retention check	After a certain time (few weeks/months) ask learners to provide a short text (analysis of a case, short essay on an ethics topic/question). Compare the levels of understanding to another piece collected during or right after the training.	SOLO taxonomy, content criteria
Vignettes	This can be used for measuring ethical sensitivity in (non-)training context	statistics, EASM (based on the SOLO taxonomy), content criteria
National surveys	Can be used for analysing training-related content in reports and monitoring the display of REI leadership.	statistics, REI leadership framework

Table 2: Tools and analytical instruments for collecting learning outputs in researchethics and integrity training

Evaluation tools can give further insight into the effectiveness of the training and materials proposed. This will help trainers to adjust training content and delivery methods to improve trainees' learning experience and outcomes. We propose mixing various tools for collecting learning outputs and adjusting them to the intended target groups (sections below provide suggestions on which tools would be most suitable for various target groups).

3. Teaching methods for strengthening research ethics and integrity

Although the teaching methods described below are presented in different sub-sections, they are closely related and can be used together when training students or more senior academics.

Effective RE/RI training benefits from active learning, reflective practices, experiential learning, and ongoing feedback (Löfström & Tammeleht, 2023 citing: Bagdasarov et al., 2012; Johnson et al., 2012; Quintana et al. 2004; Reiser, 2004; Tammeleht et al., 2021). Below is a state-of-the art overview of **methods and approaches to teaching, which according to extant research, are the best ways to support learning in the context of research ethics and integrity**. These methods and approaches described below are all compatible with the training materials and resources produced within the selected EU-funded projects. Indeed, many of the activities described in the project materials draw on a case-based approach, scaffolding and collaborative learning. To underpin the use of these methods and approaches, we provide an overview of why and how they support RE/RI learning, so that trainers may make their teaching choice based on research evidence.

3.1 Case-based approach

Across disciplines, case-based learning (CBL) is a well-established method that encourages higher levels of cognition by having students apply their knowledge to real-world or fictional situations (see Bloom's Taxonomy or Relational/extended abstract levels of learning in SOLO taxonomy). Learners usually work in groups on case studies, which are narratives with one or more characters and/or scenarios. The cases pose a disciplinary issue or issues, to which learners come up with remedies while working with an instructor (Case-Based Learning, 2024; Löfström & Tammeleht, 2023; Tammeleht et al., 2019). Case studies are an effective teaching tool that engages learners, stimulates critical thinking, and enables a deeper understanding of real-life situations. The use of case studies is a deliberate process designed to promote active engagement, critical thinking, and deeper understanding among students. Prior research (e.g., Löfström & Tammeleht, 2023 citing: Bagdasarov et al., 2012; Johnson et al., 2012; McWilliams & Nahavandi, 2006; Nonis & Swift, 2001; O'Leary & Cotter, 2000) has identified the use of cases to be beneficial in RE/RI teaching/learning. Understanding why and how learning occurs is essential for improving teaching,

and as a result, understanding how learners learn can be accessed through an awareness of learning within the framework of research ethics and integrity (Löfström & Tammeleht, 2023). It begins with the careful selection of relevant case studies that align with the learning objectives of the course. These cases should not only be current and authentic but should also reflect the students' interests and experiences and provide them with a tangible connection to the course material. RE/RI case-studies can be easily found on the online platform [the Embassy of Good Science](#).

Once a suitable case study has been selected, the teaching process usually begins with an introduction to the case (e.g., providing context and background information. This first step is crucial to ensuring that students understand the importance of the case study and its relevance to the wider course material. This practice will help students to get acquainted with the topic. In addition to case-studies, also vignettes have been used in RE/RI education to reflect on real-life situations including an explicit or implicit conflict. Trainers may identify a specific ethical/integrity issue on which learners are asked to reflect on (Löfström & Tammeleht, 2023).

As learners delve into the case study, they are asked to actively engage with the material. This means more than just passive reading; learners are encouraged to take notes, ask questions, and identify important themes or patterns contained in the case study. By promoting active reading practises, instructors aim to encourage the development of deeper understanding of the complexity of real-world problems and the various factors at play.

The initial reading is often followed by common discussion and analysis. With the guidance of the trainer, learners are encouraged to share their interpretations of the case study and explore different perspectives. Discussions can be structured around questions, which encourage critical thinking, consider alternative viewpoints and evaluate the implications of different approaches in order to move from uni- and multistructural levels to relational and extended abstract levels.

Central to the case study approach is the opportunity for learners to apply theoretical concepts and principles to real-life situations. Instructors help learners make connections between the case study and the course material by encouraging them to analyse the case through the lens of relevant theories, models or frameworks. This process not only deepens students' understanding of theoretical concepts, but also enhances their ability to apply these concepts in practical contexts.

In addition, case studies provide a platform to foster problem-solving skills. Learners are tasked with finding creative solutions to the challenges presented in the case, evaluating the feasibility of various options, and developing a reasoned plan of action. Through this process, learners learn to deal with complex problems, weigh competing interests, and make informed decisions based on facts and analyses.

Finally, case studies can serve as a valuable assessment tool, allowing instructors to evaluate learners' mastery of the content of the course and their ability to apply theoretical concepts to real-world scenarios. Assignments may include written reflections, group presentations, or class discussions based on the case study so that students can demonstrate their learning and receive constructive feedback from fellow students and instructors.

Case-based approaches are utilised in ENERI, RID-SSISS, Path2Integrity, INTEGRITY and VIRT²UE.

3.2. Collaborative learning

Collaborative learning is a pedagogical approach that emphasises active participation, shared responsibility and mutual support among students. Collaborative learning is based on the idea that the production and internalization of the knowledge is established by collaboration. Moreover, learning is usually best supported through social negotiation rather than competition. Furthermore, team learning has been demonstrated to significantly enhance ethical practice. Research indicates that students primarily interpret their socialisation into academia and their field by the ethical standards and practices that they observe (Löfström & Tammeleht, 2023; Tammeleht et al., 2022; Tammeleht et al., 2019).

When teaching research ethics and integrity, collaborative learning can be particularly effective as it can promote deeper understanding, critical thinking and ethical reasoning skills. In collaborative learning environments, students are actively engaged in the learning process rather than passively receiving information. They participate in discussions, debates and hands-on activities that require them to grapple with ethical dilemmas, analyse complex issues and apply ethical principles to real-world scenarios. This active engagement promotes deeper learning and retention of ethical concepts and principles. Collaborative learning encourages students to critically evaluate information, perspectives and arguments related to research ethics and integrity. Through discussions with peers, analysing case studies and reflecting on their own ethical beliefs and values, learners develop the

ability to identify ethical issues, consider alternative viewpoints and make informed decisions (Löfström & Tammeleht, 2023; Tammeleht et al., 2022; Tammeleht et al., 2019).

Collaborative learning environments provide opportunities for learners to challenge assumptions, explore ethical complexity and develop reasoned arguments based on evidence and ethical principles. Peer interaction is a central component of collaborative learning that allows learners to learn from each other's experiences, perspectives, and insights. By participating in discussions, debates, and collaborative projects with their peers, learners learn about various viewpoints, cultural perspectives, and disciplinary approaches to research ethics and integrity. Peer interaction also fosters collaboration, communication skills and teamwork, which are essential for addressing ethical challenges in research environments where collaboration and interdisciplinary cooperation are increasingly common (Löfström & Tammeleht, 2023; Tammeleht et al., 2022; Tammeleht et al., 2019).

During collaborating trainings, a variety of teaching methods can be used. Prior research has addressed collaborative learning with the use of case-based approaches, storytelling, flipped classroom, and role play and games (e.g., [Rotterdam dilemma game](#)) (Koterwas et al., 2021; Löfström, 2016; Tammeleht et al., 2019; Tammeleht et al., 2022).

Collaborative approaches are utilised in Path2Integrity, INTEGRITY and VIRT²UE.

3.3. Scaffolding and feedback

[Scaffolding](#) is a teaching technique, which involves providing tailored support to learners based on their current expertise and gradually withdrawing support as they become more proficient. This approach, researched in the context of research ethics and integrity, is used in both face-to-face and online learning environments, including problem-based and inquiry learning (Quintana et al. 2004; Reiser, 2004; Tammeleht et al., 2021). Conceptual scaffolding is crucial in problem-based and inquiry learning, helping learners navigate complex concepts and considering various learning styles. Teachers can adjust academic content to suit learners' abilities. Online courses benefit from personalized learning paths that can be adjusted in real-time. Scaffolding aligns with the idea of [Vygotsky's zone of proximal development](#), that is instruction and facilitation should target the

domain where the learner can function with assistance. It is unnecessary to provide scaffolding in domains which the learner already masters, or which are still beyond the learners reach.

When teaching research ethics and integrity, scaffolding entails dissecting difficult ideas into smaller, more digestible chunks and supporting students as they gain knowledge. [Scaffolding](#) can be planned into the design of the course teaching/learning activities and the instructions of these, but often opportunities to incorporate scaffolding techniques present themselves ad hoc. In this case, it is important that the trainer is aware of a variety of techniques and recognises situations in which they can be beneficially used to support learning. The steps for incorporating scaffolding include:

1. Identifying what the learner already knows, that is, what is their current level and where is the zone of proximal development;
2. Setting goals, which reflect the learning objectives, for the learner in line with what was determined to be within reach in the prior step;
3. Planning a suitable breakdown of goals and activities in support of the goals;
4. Carrying out the training with scaffolding, monitoring of learning and provision of feedback during the learning;
5. Adjusting the support and gradually decreasing it as the learner progresses towards the goal;
6. new goals and planning activities as the prior goals are reached.

For example the website [Scaffolding Over Time](https://www.buffalo.edu/catt.html) (<https://www.buffalo.edu/catt.html> prepared by the Office of Curriculum and Teaching Transformation, University of Buffalo provides more information on Scaffolding for the trainer interested in using this technique.

[Table 3 presents a scaffolding framework utilised in research ethics training \(Tammeleht et al., 2020\).](#)

Scaffolding process	Scaffolding mechanism	Scaffolding technique	Scaffolding purpose	Illustrative example

SENSE MAKING	Problematizing	Hinting	Give an indirect suggestion or piece of evidence that leads toward a problem solution (Merriam-Webster)	'So, the documents pertaining to research ethics and integrity to consult would be...' (implying that some documents should be consulted)
	Problematizing	Describing the problem to direct focus	Orient to the important features (Tambaum, 2017)	'Indeed, when you have to get an informed consent you should consider various aspects, for example ...'
	Structural/ Problematizing	Making fill-in-the-blank kinds of requests	A statement or a question with a missing component (but some info is given)	'A good way to highlight the importance of research integrity would be to?'
	Structural/ Problematizing	Asking a leading question (P – why?)	A question that prompts or encourages the answer wanted	'Where can you find the information pertaining to the codes of conduct?'
	Structural	Providing an example	Giving an example to illustrate a point	'For example, in Europe it is a common practice to consult a research integrity advisor.'
	Structural	Providing physical props	Helping to understand by mimicking or showing a visual aid	'What do you think are the ethical aspects of designing this item?' (show e.g. a fork)
PROCESS MANAGEMENT	Structural	Pumping	Simulating to go further without specific instructions (Tambaum, 2017)	'OK, what else?'
	Structural	Redirecting the learner	Showing which direction to go, which aspect should be tackled next (especially when seeing that the direction is lost/off)	'All right, let's get back to the track and discuss the next steps of the ethics review process'
	Structural	Decomposing the task	Making the bigger task into smaller components	'First, think what you know about the ethics review process, then, read the paragraph and finally...' (give instructions one task after another)
	Structural	Initiating the reasoning step	Use the faculty of reason so as to arrive at conclusions	'What happened first was ..., and then you ..., what do you think should happen next to solve this dilemma?'
	Structural	Completing the learners' reasoning	'Splicing in' the correct answer (Tambaum, 2017)	(the learner cannot end the thought) '... you mean a code of conduct should be consulted?'

ARTICULATION & REFLECTION	Structural	Executing parts of the skill	Do parts of the task for the learner to give an example	'OK, so first you consult the ALLEA code of conduct and then ...'
	Structural	Maintaining goal orientation	Reminding the learner of some aspect of the task	'Have you also had time to think about ...?'
	Structural/ Problematizing	Highlighting critical features	Drawing attention to the most important aspects of the problem; highlighting 'discrepancies' (Reiser, 2004)	'Do you remember you mentioned the ethics review, what other purposes might it have?'
	Problematizing	Comparing the current problem with a previously solved one	Showing similarities between solutions	'Do you recall the situation that happened to Dr Smith when he invited participants into his survey? This situation may actually have similar implications.'

Table 3: Scaffolding framework utilised in research ethics training.

Offering feedback and facilitating reflection are critical components when using scaffolding in research ethics and integrity training.

Feedback is more effective (Brinko, 1993):

- when given as soon as possible after the session,
- when it is focused,
- when considered as a process, not a one-time shot,
- when receivers participate in the feedback process freely or when doing so is required by regular professional standards,
- when it has a restricted and chosen number of negative comments mixed in with a decent number of positive and encouraging remarks.
- when negative information is "sandwiched" between positive information,
- when it allows the receiver to respond and interact,
- when given frequently, but not excessively,
- when it creates cognitive [dissonance](#) (Van Lange et al., 2012),

Feedback can be provided by the trainer as well as by peers. Peer feedback is effective (Brinko, 1993):

- when information is gathered from different people,
- when it is believed that the information's source is reliable, informed, and has a good intention,
- when the status or career level of the feedback provider and its' recipient are the same

Scaffolding techniques are utilised in RID-SSISS, ROSiE, VIRT2UE, INTEGRITY, Path2Integrity, and in the Case studies section of ENERI Classroom.

4. Training material

In this section you will find examples of training materials on research ethics and integrity that can be used to train at specific career stages. In the following we introduce a collection of trainings developed by EU-funded initiatives and indicate, which trainings or parts of them are suitable for 1) secondary schools, 2) bachelor and master students, 3) PhD students and early career researchers, 4) academics and experts in research ethics and integrity, and 5) supervisors. Although we have categorised the training materials by career stage, we recommend that trainers and teachers define the needs and skill level of the group to be trained before selecting the material to be used. This is because career stage often does not reflect the level of skills and competences in terms of research ethics and integrity. In addition, in this section you will find examples of training materials that focus on open science practises. In this case, the training materials are not categorised by career level as they apply to all. The following training resources have been developed by EU-funded initiatives namely: PRINTEGER, ENERI, RID-SSISS, EnTIRE, VIRT²UE, Path2Integrity, INTEGRITY, BRIDGE and ROSiE.

This Trainer Guide offers an intuitive roadmap for users to navigate complex topics and utilize resources developed under different EU-funded projects.

All the training resources presented below, provide examples of training materials to promote RE/RI and prevent research misconduct from the perspective of individual and institutional responsibilities. Active learning, like case studies, engages learners and helps connect content to real ethical dilemmas. Reflection helps learners explore personal values, making ethical principles and theories more meaningful and guiding individual growth. Role-playing and simulations offer experiential insights, allowing learners to practice decision-making in a safe environment, fostering

empathy and ethical confidence. A culturally sensitive approach prepares learners for global collaboration by recognizing diverse ethical norms. Lastly, continuous assessment and constructive feedback reinforce learning, enabling learners to apply ethical principles thoughtfully in real-life scenarios, supporting long-term commitment to research integrity.

Moreover, trainers will be able to assess the effectiveness of the different training modules by using tools and methods to measure the short-, medium- and long-term impact of RE/RI trainings (presented below). While materials and resources have been developed for RE/RI training, they may not always include a plan for the assessment of learning or suggestions on how information about learning can be used as an indicator of training effect.

To enhance the structure of the training material, it can be divided not only by career level but also by type of training activity and by the specific EU project responsible for its development. This alternative categorization (presented in Appendix 1) allows for a more tailored approach, enabling users to quickly identify relevant resources that align with their needs, when they already know what training approaches they wish to use, or seeking further guidance related to using specific teaching approaches rather than seeking resources for a specific target group. By connecting each piece of training material to its originating EU project, we can highlight the distinct contributions of each initiative, showcasing their unique approaches to training.

4.1 Training materials for secondary schools

In this section we introduce a selection of material suitable to train secondary school students. The aim of educating secondary school students is to raise their awareness of the ethical and integrity challenges they may face. Empowering students to behave responsibly in research is at the heart of the [INTEGRITY](#) course and each individual module. The [modules](#) presented are: 1) animal experimentation; 2) art, activism and awareness; 3) data transmission; 4) epidemiology; 5) fast fashion; 6) genotyping testing; 7) music-sounds in the age of social media; 8) space exploration; and 9) technology. The training materials are presented alongside a [Teacher Guide](#).

The [Path2Integrity](#) project introduces educators to innovative teaching methods that will take topics in Research Integrity and Ethics. The project provides introductory videos and information on the teaching methodology used, discussing research integrity and its significance. These materials can

be found in the [Path2Integrity Training Programme](#) section. The project developed a series of learning cards ([Path2Integrity learning cards S](#)) focusing on students in high schools, alongside a dedicated handbook ([S-Series handbook](#)).

For training effectiveness measurement facilitators can use the following tools for learning output collection and for analysing collected material:

Tool for collecting learning outputs	Details	Analysis instrument **
ProLearning app	<i>ProLearning</i> : www.prolearning.realto.ch	learning analytics
Engagement app	<i>ForgetNot</i> (by EduLog): https://web.htk.tlu.ee/forgetnot	learning analytics
Self-Reflection Form/Compass	App under development, form * (for copying and editing)	SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels, content criteria
Pre-post texts	Collect a short text (e.g. a response to a case or short essay) before the training and after the training	SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels, content criteria
Learning diaries	Ask learners keep a diary over a certain period, for each submission provide some guiding questions or topics	SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels, content criteria
Group reports	Ask groups working together to provide a (short) group report (or provide a template with points to work on)	SOLO taxonomy, content criteria

Group discussions	Monitor the group discussions to evaluate the level of understanding and content discussed (scaffold as appropriate)	SOLO taxonomy, content criteria
Group dynamics	<i>CoTrack</i> application: https://www.cotrack.website/en/	learning analytics
Retention check	After a certain time (few weeks/months) ask learners to provide a short text (analysis of a case, short essay on an ethics topic/question). Compare the levels of understanding to another piece collected during or right after the training.	SOLO taxonomy, content criteria

Table 4: BEYOND Tools for evaluating training effectiveness for secondary-school students

* The Self-Reflection Form link enables the facilitator to make a copy of the form, which they can then edit, and the data will accumulate on the facilitator’s cloud service (Google or Microsoft).

** Analysis instruments are described in WP4.2, later available at the Embassy’s website.

For instance, to measure participants’ reactions during or right after the training, *ProLearning* app or *Self-Reflection Form* can be used. In addition, if learners worked in groups and provided a group-report, the learning process can be evaluated based on the SOLO taxonomy to measure the levels of understanding. Moreover, if possible, a couple of months after the training an additional case study could be given to the same learners, and the content of their analysis could again be evaluated with the SOLO taxonomy. This kind of effectiveness measure would give a possibility to triangulate the measurement in different time points.

4.2 Training materials for bachelor and master students

In this section we introduce a selection of material suitable to train bachelor and master students. The aim of training students in research ethics and integrity is to promote an understanding of ethical principles and practices in research. This includes exploring aspects of honesty, transparency, objectivity and accountability. Although at these levels, students are marginally involved in doing research, it is important to equip them with the knowledge and skills to conduct research responsibly, avoid misconduct such as plagiarism or falsification, comply with relevant regulations and guidelines, and uphold the integrity of the scientific community.

4.2.1 Introducing research ethics and integrity

The [Upright training](#) developed by the [PRINTEGER](#) projects provides the opportunity to have an overview of common research integrity issues in the academia. The training programme has been developed with the aim of raising awareness among “newcomers” to RI and RE. Besides providing knowledge and information on the topic, the training programme contributes to the development of the moral character of researchers by encouraging reflection on specific dilemmas and cases.

With its [introductory module](#), it aims to give students a first look at why research integrity matters. This module is based on the film *On Being A Scientist*, produced by the Leiden University. This provides a rough overview of the subject and can be found here: [On Being A Scientist](#). The film *On Being A Scientist* can be split up into nine episodes. Each episode focuses on a specific topic. The movie can be also found [here](#).

The e-learning modules produced by the [VIRT²UE](#) project represent an introduction to relevant topics in research integrity. These modules, which foster self-learning introduce [research integrity](#), [virtue ethics relevant for RI and](#) virtue ethics under current research conditions. Moreover, the training has developed a series of [videos](#) introducing specific concepts and themes relevant to the field and practice of research integrity, such as ethical decision making in research and moral disengagement in research.

The [Path2Integrity](#) project introduces educators to innovative teaching methods that will take topics in Research Integrity and Ethics. The project provides introductory videos and information on the

teaching methodology used, discussing research integrity and its significance. These materials can be found in the [Path2Integrity Training Programme](#) section.

4.2.2 Exploring modules on research ethics and integrity topics

Besides the introductory module, the Upright training provides [modules](#) focusing specifically on RE and/or RI issues. These modules address topics in relation to research misconduct, questionable research practices and more research ethics-related topics. Depending on the complexity of the topic, these modules can be used for students and academics with different levels of RE/RI-related competencies.

The RID-SSISS training aims to help beginner and more experienced researchers develop their research ethics competencies in HE institutions. A CSCL (Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning) ethics resource was designed that utilised cases, collaboration, and structural scaffolding. This resource provides learners with opportunities to gradually develop research ethics competencies, guiding them through three levels. The [Foundation level](#) focuses on developing (but also helping learners to recall) central concepts of RE/RI, primarily suitable for bachelor's, master's, and doctoral students but also usable with academic staff and researchers. During the Foundation level training, participants learn to guide their own REI practices and behaviour.

The [BRIDGE project](#) provides [training modules](#) and [vignettes](#) that can be inserted into research ethics and integrity courses.

4.2.3 Learning cards

Using the [Path2Integrity](#) learning materials and methods in an adaptable and sustainable manner is the main goal of the Path2Integrity training programme for educators (P2ITE), which aims to improve educators' and teachers' competencies, confidence, and abilities to teach research integrity effectively. This includes engaging and creative teaching and learning techniques like role-playing and storytelling. The project developed a series of learning cards ([Path2Integrity learning cards S](#)) focusing on bachelor students, alongside a dedicated handbook ([S-Series handbook](#)), and a series of learning cards ([Path2Integrity learning cards M](#)) focusing on master students, alongside a dedicated handbook ([M-Series handbook](#)).

4.2.4 Research ethics and integrity games

The goal of [INTEGRITY](#) is to empower students and early career researchers. Rather than focusing on compliance, the project's first approach is to develop the capacity of participants to identify, consider, and address integrity concerns in research procedures. Central to empowerment are three fundamental components. The initiative considers that students see and experience academic and research integrity challenges differently throughout their careers depending on their circumstances since, first and foremost, empowering students is about localization. It is necessary for students to be able to cultivate a critical autonomy, or an attitude of reflection on their own actions and experiences. Empowerment stimulates a pro-active attitude in participants of the courses, helping them to actively address and deal with integrity issues they encounter in their studies or research. The project developed a specific training tool for [undergraduate](#).

The training games developed the [BRIDGE project](#) use the “gamification” approach as a learning approach to raise awareness and provide very basic knowledge on RI, focusing on undergraduates and graduates. The aim of these training is to promote knowledge and awareness on the topics of research ethics and integrity in undergraduates. Online games, board games, role-play games and scenarios game can be found [here](#).

The [Modified Dilemma Game](#) developed by the [VIRT²UE](#) project presents a modified version of the [Dilemma Game](#) developed by Erasmus University Rotterdam. This exercise supports participants in identifying research integrity principles, virtues and questionable research practices in a hypothetical case. It provides a framework to consider, choose and defend alternative courses of action regarding realistic research integrity dilemmas.

4.2.5 Training materials on Open Science

This sub-section presents training materials focusing on open science. By imparting the essential knowledge and cultivating skills and attitudes, the [ROSiE](#) Training Materials for Responsible Open Science aim to teach researchers how to perform open science responsibly and prevent research misconduct within the framework of open science. Utilizing online training resources is another way to put blended learning into practice. This method mixes traditional in-person instruction with

the usage of the internet to let students create their own learning experiences. Trainees can gain from direction and engagement with a trainer while having access to flexible and interactive training options outside of the classroom by combining in-person and online training methods. The 'conventional' learning resources produced by the ROSIE project (refer to the [ROSiE Knowledge Hub](#)) can be utilized in conjunction with the online training resources for self-directed learning developed by ROSiE to facilitate blended learning in the classroom.

Training materials on responsible open science can be found for the fields of [Social Sciences](#), [Natural Sciences](#), [Humanities](#), [Health and Life Sciences](#) and [Citizen Science](#). In addition, the ROSiE project created a [collection of case studies](#) that can be use in the traditional and/or online ROSiE training. Moreover, six different modules on responsible open science can be found [here](#), on the Embassy of Good Science platform.

4.2.6 Training materials on the responsible use of AI

As artificial intelligence (AI) becomes increasingly integrated into our lives and work, it is important to ensure that its development and use is both ethical and responsible. This guide is designed to help educators educate individuals and organizations about the principles and practices of responsible AI. With this section we want to help trainers to convey the importance of fairness, transparency and ethical considerations in AI systems, fostering a deeper understanding and commitment to responsible AI among their participants. Although training materials focusing on AI are still in development, we hope to give trainers insight on possible material to be used. There are different ways of using AI, not only to generate text, but also to work with your own material (proofreading, changing style, transcription). Researchers should be transparent about how they have used AI tools, as they would be about any other tools and methods. The most important requirement for any researcher is to CHECK the material generated by AI, for example in a systematic review.

Most of the resources available are made by recommendations and guidelines on the use of responsible AI. Published by the European Commission, the [Living Guidelines on the Responsible Use of Generative AI in Research](#) provides recommendations for researchers, research institutions and funding organizations. [ENAI](#) developed [a practical guide for students](#) (see also [here](#)) on the use of generative AI. [UKRIO](#) provides a full list of resources on [the use of AI in research](#).

Trainers should also consider the implication in case learners use AI to do the tasks created as part of different programs. We provide one example of what the outcome could be at the end of the guide. (See Appendix 7.2).

Tool for collecting learning outputs	Details	Analysis instrument **
ProLearning app	<i>ProLearning</i> : www.prolearning.realto.ch	learning analytics
Engagement app	<i>ForgetNot</i> (by EduLog): https://web.htk.tlu.ee/forgetnot	learning analytics
Self-Reflection Form/Compass	App under development, form * (for copying and editing)	SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels, content criteria
Pre-post texts	Collect a short text (e.g. a response to a case or short essay) before the training and after the training	SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels, content criteria
Learning diaries	Ask learners keep a diary over a certain period, for each submission provide some guiding questions or topics	SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels, content criteria
Group reports	Ask groups working together to provide a (short) group report (or provide a template with points to work on)	SOLO taxonomy, content criteria
Group discussions	Monitor the group discussions to evaluate the level of understanding	SOLO taxonomy, content criteria

	and content discussed (scaffold as appropriate)	
Group dynamics	<i>CoTrack</i> application: https://www.cotrack.website/en/	learning analytics
Online learning platform	Make use of accumulated authentic learning outputs in the learning platform.	statistics, SOLO taxonomy, reflection scale, content criteria
Domain-specific/domain-transcending measure	Use either of the two forms (WP4.2) measuring recognition and exemplifying of ethical issues.	statistics, SOLO taxonomy, content criteria
Retention check	After a certain time (few weeks/months) ask learners to provide a short text (analysis of a case, short essay on an ethics topic/question). Compare the levels of understanding to another piece collected during or right after the training.	SOLO taxonomy, content criteria

Table5: Tools for evaluating training effectiveness for bachelor and master students

* The Self-Reflection Form link enables the facilitator to make a copy of the form, which they can then edit and the data will accumulate on the facilitator’s cloud service (Google or Microsoft).

** Analysis instruments are described in WP4.2, later available at the Embassy’s website.

For instance, to measure participants’ reactions during or right after the training, *ProLearning* app or *Self-Reflection Form* can be used. In addition, if learners worked in groups so their group discussions can be monitored, and if they provided a group-report, the learning process can be evaluated based on the SOLO taxonomy to measure the levels of understanding. Moreover, if possible, a couple of months after the training an additional case study could be given to the same

learners, and the content of their analysis could again be evaluated with the SOLO taxonomy. With this target group the domain-specific and domain-transcending measure could be implemented. This kind of effectiveness measure would give a possibility to triangulate the measurement in different time points.

An example for implementation can be found here: [ENERI CR material example for ba_ma students.pptx](#)

4.3 Training materials for doctoral students and early career researchers

In this section we introduce a selection of material suitable to train doctoral students and early career researchers. The goal in training students and PhD candidates in RE/RI is to support ever-deepening understanding of ethical principles and practices in research. This includes exploring aspects of honesty, transparency, objectivity and accountability at all stages of the research process, from conception to dissemination of results. The goal is to equip students with the knowledge and skills to conduct research responsibly, avoid misconduct such as plagiarism or falsification, comply with relevant regulations and guidelines, and uphold the integrity of the scientific community.

Although these examples can be used to train students and PhD candidates, they can be used in training more senior profiles to brush up competencies on the topic.

4.3.1 Introducing research ethics and integrity

The [Upright training](#) developed by the [PRINTEGER](#) projects provides the opportunity to have an overview of common research integrity issues in the academia. The training programme has been developed with the aim of raising awareness among “newcomers” to RI and RE. Besides providing knowledge and information on the topic, the training programme contributes to the development of the moral character of researchers by encouraging reflection on specific dilemmas and cases.

With its [introductory module](#), it aims to give students a first look at why research integrity matters. This module is based on the film *On Being A Scientist*, produced by the Leiden University. This provides a rough overview of the subject and can be found here: [On Being A Scientist](#). The film *On*

Being A Scientist can be split up into nine episodes. Each episode focuses on a specific topic. The movie can be also found [here](#).

The e-learning modules produced by the [VIRT²UE](#) project represent an introduction to relevant topics in research integrity. These modules, which foster self-learning introduce [research integrity](#), [virtue ethics relevant for RI and](#) virtue ethics under current research conditions. Moreover, the training has developed a series of [videos](#) introducing specific concepts and themes relevant to the field and practice of research integrity, such as ethical decision making in research and moral disengagement in research.

The [Path2Integrity](#) project introduces educators to innovative teaching methods that will take topics in Research Integrity and Ethics. The project provides introductory videos and information on the teaching methodology used, discussing research integrity and its significance. These materials can be found in the [Path2Integrity Training Programme](#) section.

4.3.2 Exploring modules on research ethics and integrity topics

Besides the introductory module, the Upright training provides [modules](#) focusing specific RE and/or RI issues. These modules address topics in relation the research misconduct, questionable research practices and more research ethics-related topics. Depending on the complexity of the topic, these modules can be used for students and academics with different levels of RE/RI-related competencies.

The RID-SSISS training for ECRs and junior academics aims to develop RE/RI competencies by supporting ethical analysis competencies as a step towards increased agency in research ethics and integrity. Ethical analysis involves the following steps: identify ethical issues by determining which ethical principle might be at stake; and utilise the ethical analysis steps to provide solutions to ethical dilemmas. In addition to the foundational level, the project developed training materials for ECRs and junior academics ([advanced level](#)).

The [BRIDGE project](#) provides [training modules](#) and [vignettes](#) that can be inserted into research ethics and integrity courses.

Other [modules and a full interactive training](#) have been developed by the [INTEGRITY](#) project. The goal of INTEGRITY is to empower students and early career researchers. Rather than focusing on

compliance, the project's first approach is to develop the capacity of participants to identify, consider, and address integrity concerns in research procedures. Central to empowerment are three fundamental components. The initiative considers that students see and experience academic and research integrity challenges differently throughout their careers depending on their circumstances since, first and foremost, empowering students is about localization. It is necessary for students to be able to cultivate a critical autonomy, or an attitude of reflection on their own actions and experiences. Empowerment stimulates a pro-active attitude in participants of the courses, helping them to actively address and deal with integrity issues they encounter in their studies or research.

4.3.3 Learning cards

Using the [Path2Integrity](#) learning materials and methods in an adaptable and sustainable manner is the main goal of the Path2Integrity training programme for educators (P2ITE), which aims to improve educators' and teachers' competencies, confidence, and abilities to teach research integrity effectively. This includes engaging and creative teaching and learning techniques like role-playing and storytelling. The project developed a series of learning cards ([Path2Integrity learning cards Y](#)) focusing on doctoral students, alongside a dedicated handbook ([Y-Series handbook](#)).

The [Modified Dilemma Game](#) developed by the [VIRT²UE](#) project presents a modified version of the [Dilemma Game](#) developed by Erasmus University Rotterdam. This exercise supports participants in identifying research integrity principles, virtues and questionable research practices in a hypothetical case. It provides a framework to consider, choose and defend alternative courses of action regarding realistic research integrity dilemmas.

4.3.4 Case studies

Besides providing an overview of the main RE/RI topics the [Upright training](#) gives the opportunity to reflect on several dilemmas from the “[Dilemma Game. Professionalism and Integrity in Research](#)”. Specifically, the Upright training proposes the following dilemmas: [With a little help](#), [Mutual favours](#), [Sharing data](#), [So close](#), [Different results](#), [Put your supervisor first](#), [Flexible scope](#), [Outliers](#), and [Invalid data](#).

The EnTIRE project created eight scenarios, each of which presented a fictitious story along with eight distinct themes. The content on the Embassy of Science site includes several scenarios. Teachers can demonstrate important concepts through fiction without having to worry about providing accurate facts. You can discover frequent errors and what distinguishes exceptional researchers by utilising simple scenarios. The purpose of the scenarios is to provide researchers, research ethics committees (RECs), research integrity offices (RIOs), and research administrators with an enhanced understanding of The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ECCRI or ECoC), a regulatory document that outlines the recommended practices for conducting ethical research. In addition, they let users consider and implement their own institutional and national codes of ethics and integrity for research as well as other important regulations. The user's understanding of the standards linked to ethical research methods and their application in various research scenarios are the main objectives. The purpose of each of the eight scenarios is to provide RECs, research administrators, researchers, and researchers with the opportunity to concentrate their attention on the fundamental ideas and research settings that support both local regulations and practices and effective research practices. The scenarios developed are the following: [Research Procedures and Research Integrity](#); [Collaborative Working Between Academia and Industry](#); [Data Practices, Data Management and FAIR Principles](#); [Publication, Dissemination and Research Integrity](#); [Research Environments and Research Integrity](#); [Reviewing, Evaluating, Editing and Research Integrity](#); [Training, Supervision and Mentoring with Integrity](#); [Safeguards, Data-sharing and the Disclosure of Sensitive Results](#).

4.3.5 Virtue-ethics based training

The [VIRT²UE](#) project designed a training programme with a virtue ethics approach to Ethics and Research Integrity (ERI). In particular, the VIRT2UE training supports participants in creating closer connections between ERI guidelines and codes, in particular the European Code of Conduct for Research integrity (ECoC); acquire theoretical knowledge about ERI and virtues; and be exposed to moral challenges related to real cases from the profession of a researcher. The project developed different modules focusing on trainees (students and PhD candidates) approaching for the first time the topic. The modules introducing [research integrity](#), [virtue ethics relevant for RI](#) and

[virtue ethics to foster research culture](#). Moreover, it provides introductory [readings](#) and [videos](#) to specific concepts and themes.

The VIRT2UE training programme is a blended learning program that consists of four components: it initiates with an online course (consisting of three modules mentioned above), proceeds with a face-to-face participatory session (consisting of five modules/exercises): [Debate and Dialogue](#), [Virtues and Norms](#), [The Middle Position](#), the [Modified Dilemma Game](#), and the [Self-Declaration Approach](#).

4.3.6 Training materials on Open Science

This sub-section presents training materials focusing on open science. By imparting the essential knowledge and cultivating particular skills and attitudes, the [ROSiE](#) Training Materials for Responsible Open Science aim to teach researchers how to perform open science responsibly and prevent research misconduct within the framework of open science. Utilizing online training resources is another way to put blended learning into practice. This method mixes traditional in-person instruction with the usage of the internet to let students create their own learning experiences. Trainees can gain from direction and engagement with a trainer while having access to flexible and interactive training options outside of the classroom by combining in-person and online training methods. The 'conventional' learning resources produced by the ROSiE project (refer to the [ROSiE Knowledge Hub](#)) can be utilized in conjunction with the online training resources for self-directed learning developed by ROSiE to facilitate blended learning in the classroom.

Training materials on responsible open science can be found for the fields of [Social Sciences](#), [Natural Sciences](#), [Humanities](#), [Health and Life Sciences](#) and [Citizen Science](#). In addition, the ROSiE project created a [collection of case studies](#) that can be use in the traditional and/or online ROSiE training. Moreover, six different modules on responsible open science can be found [here](#), on the Embassy of Good Science platform.

4.3.7 Training materials on the responsible use of AI

As artificial intelligence (AI) becomes increasingly integrated into our lives and work, it is important to ensure that its development and use is both ethical and responsible. This guide is

designed to help educators educate individuals and organizations about the principles and practices of responsible AI. With this section we want to help trainers to convey the importance of fairness, transparency and ethical considerations in AI systems, fostering a deeper understanding and commitment to responsible AI among their participants. Although training materials focusing on AI are still in development, we hope to give trainers insight on possible material to be used. There are different ways of using AI, not only to generate text, but also to work with your own material (proofreading, changing style, transcription). Researchers should be transparent about how they have used AI tools, as they would be about any other tools and methods. The most important requirement for any researcher is to CHECK the material generated by AI, for example in a systematic review.

Most of the resources available are made by recommendations and guidelines on the use of responsible AI. Published by the European Commission, the [Living Guidelines on the Responsible Use of Generative AI in Research](#) provides recommendations for researchers, research institutions and funding organizations. [ENAI](#) developed [a practical guide for students](#) (see also [here](#)) on the use of generative AI. [UKRIO](#) provides a full list of resources on [the use of AI in research](#).

Trainers should also consider the implication in case learners use AI to do the tasks created as part of different programs. We provide one example of what the outcome could be at the end of the guide (Appendix 7.2).

Tool for collecting learning outputs	Details	Analysis instrument **
Self-Reflection Form/Compass	App under development, form * (for copying and editing)	SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels, content criteria
Pre-post texts	Collect a short text (e.g. a response to a case or short essay) before the training and after the training	SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels, content criteria
Learning diaries	Ask learners keep a diary over a certain period, for each submission provide some guiding questions or topics	SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels, content criteria

Group reports	Ask groups working together to provide a (short) group report (or provide a template with points to work on)	SOLO taxonomy, content criteria
Group discussions	Monitor the group discussions to evaluate the level of understanding and content discussed (scaffold as appropriate)	SOLO taxonomy, content criteria
Group dynamics	<i>CoTrack</i> application: https://www.cotrack.website/en/	learning analytics
Online learning platform	Make use of accumulated authentic learning outputs in the learning platform.	statistics, SOLO taxonomy, reflection scale, content criteria
Domain-specific/ domain-transcending measure	Use either of the two forms (WP4.2) measuring recognition and exemplifying of ethical issues.	statistics, SOLO taxonomy, content criteria
Retention check	After a certain time (few weeks/months) ask learners to provide a short text (analysis of a case, short essay on an ethics topic/question). Compare the levels of understanding to another piece collected during or right after the training.	SOLO taxonomy, content criteria
Vignettes	This can be used for measuring ethical sensitivity in (non-)training context	statistics, EASM (based on the SOLO taxonomy), content criteria
National surveys	Can be used for analysing training-related content in reports and monitoring the display of REI leadership.	statistics, REI leadership framework

Table 6: BEYOND Tools for evaluating training effectiveness for early-career researchers

* The Self-Reflection Form link enables the facilitator to make a copy of the form, which they can then edit, and the data will accumulate on the facilitator's cloud service (Google or Microsoft).

** Analysis instruments are described in WP4.2, later available at the Embassy's website.

For instance, to measure participants' reactions during or right after the training, *Self-Reflection Form* can be used. In addition, if learners worked in groups so their group discussions can be monitored, and if they provided a group-report, the learning process can be evaluated based on the SOLO taxonomy to measure the levels of understanding. Moreover, if possible, a couple of months after the training an additional case study could be given to the same learners, and the content of their analysis could again be evaluated with the SOLO taxonomy. With this target group the domain-specific and domain-transcending measure could be implemented. This kind of effectiveness measure would give a possibility to triangulate the measurement in different time points.

Examples for implementation can be found here: [ENERI CR material example for ECRs.pptx](#)

4.4 Training materials for research ethics and integrity experts.

4.4.1 Case studies

[ENERI Classroom](#) contains training material exploring research ethics and integrity issues focusing on academics, and research ethics and integrity experts. The research integrity advisory boards, committees handling allegations or working with research integrity policy development, research integrity officers and advisors, research integrity ombudspersons (RIOs), research ethics committees including their members and their secretariats (RECs), and experts and officers in EU-bodies are the main target groups of the training materials and curricula tool. These groups include both new and experienced members. Themes that experts deal with that are associated with [research integrity](#) include good scientific practice, questionable research practices, research misconduct, responsible authorship, peer review, and whistleblowing. Themes that experts on [research ethics](#) deal with include, for instance, ethics review, the protection of human rights, the safety of clinical trials, informed consent procedures, research with participants unable to consent, and the protection of animals. [Comprehensive and overlapping issues](#) involving both integrity and ethics related considerations involve, for example, data management and data protection, open data sharing, open access, transparency, fairness, reliability and credibility, and conflicts of interest. While RECs and RIOs are key actors in facilitating research ethics and integrity, there may be countries that lack

infrastructure as well as training opportunities for actors in related key positions. A specific section focusing on the [development of proper infrastructure](#) is also present.

The [Upright training](#) gives the opportunity to reflect on several dilemmas from the “[Dilemma Game. Professionalism and Integrity in Research](#)”. Specifically, the Upright training proposes the following dilemmas: [With a little help](#), [Mutual favours](#), [Sharing data](#), [So close](#), [Different results](#), [Put your supervisor first](#), [Flexible scope](#), [Outliers](#), and [Invalid data](#).

The EnTIRE project created eight scenarios, each of which presented a fictitious story along with eight distinct themes: [Research Procedures and Research Integrity](#); [Collaborative Working Between Academia and Industry](#); [Data Practices, Data Management and FAIR Principles](#); [Publication, Dissemination and Research Integrity](#); [Research Environments and Research Integrity](#); [Reviewing, Evaluating, Editing and Research Integrity](#); [Training, Supervision and Mentoring with Integrity](#); [Safeguards, Data-sharing and the Disclosure of Sensitive Results](#).

4.5 Training materials for professors and senior academics.

When training professors, trainers, mentors, and supervisors in research integrity, the aim is to equip them with the knowledge, skills, and resources to effectively train, mentor and guide their students and junior colleagues in conducting research with integrity.

4.5.1 Train-the-Trainer

The [VIRT²UE](#) project designed a Train-the-Trainer training programme with a virtue ethics approach to Ethics and Research Integrity (ERI). In particular, the VIRT²UE training supports participants in creating closer connections between ERI guidelines and codes, in particular the European Code of Conduct for Research integrity (ECoC); acquire theoretical knowledge about ERI and virtues; and be exposed to moral challenges related to real cases from the profession of a researcher. The project developed different modules introducing [research integrity](#), [virtue ethics relevant for RI](#) and [virtue ethics to foster research culture](#). Moreover, it provides introductory [readings](#) and [videos](#) to specific concepts and themes. The VIRT²UE training programme is a blended learning program that consists of four components: it initiates with an online course (consisting of three modules mentioned above), proceeds with a face-to-face participatory session

(consisting of five modules/exercises) : [Debate and Dialogue](#), [Virtues and Norms](#), [The Middle Position](#), the [Modified Dilemma Game](#), and the [Self-Declaration Approach](#). After participating in the five exercises (Debate and Dialogue, Virtues and Norms, The Middle Position, the Modified Dilemma Game, and the Self-Declaration Approach) the train-the-trainer program developed further content/exercises where future trainer can evaluate their ability to facilitate themselves a training session and the different exercises. Future trainers have to prepare, organize and facilitate the five exercises during the so-called [interim practice](#). In addition, the program foresees a [group/reflection section](#), in which future trainers can reflect on the experience. The train-the-trainer program developed precise instructions for trainers on how to prepare, organize and facilitate the section. These instructions can be found by clicking on the [Trainer tab](#) on the training webpage.

4.5.2 Supervision and mentorship practices

Researchers and Supervisors are key players in RE/RI, and the role as supervisor brings its own ethical challenges. The [INTEGRITY](#) project developed training materials to foster mentorship and supervision.

The RID-SSISS training for academics aims to develop leadership competencies by combining senior academics' extant knowledge base with RE/RI and new leadership competencies. In addition to the foundational level, and the advanced level, the RID-SSISS project developed a training for supervisors and leaders ([leadership level](#)).

The [VIRT²UE](#) project developed a training module introducing [supervision and mentorship practices](#). This module highlights the relevance of supervision, mentoring, and role-modelling in research environments and provides definitions of roles and their corresponding responsibilities.

Also the [BRIDGE project](#) developed a specific [module for supervisors](#).

Tool for collecting learning outputs	Details	Analysis instrument **
Self-Reflection Form/Compass	App under development, form * (for copying and editing)	SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels, content criteria
Pre-post texts	Collect a short text (e.g. a response to a case or short essay) before the training and after the training	SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels, content criteria
Learning diaries	Ask learners keep a diary over a certain period, for each submission provide some guiding questions or topics	SOLO taxonomy, reflection levels, content criteria
Group reports	Ask groups working together to provide a (short) group report (or provide a template with points to work on)	SOLO taxonomy, content criteria
Group discussions	Monitor the group discussions to evaluate the level of understanding and content discussed (scaffold as appropriate)	SOLO taxonomy, content criteria
Retention check	After a certain time (few weeks/months) ask learners to provide a short text (analysis of a case, short essay on an ethics topic/question). Compare the levels of understanding to another piece collected during or right after the training.	SOLO taxonomy, content criteria

Vignettes	This can be used for measuring ethical sensitivity in (non-)training context.	statistics, EASM (based on the SOLO taxonomy), content criteria
National surveys	Can be used for analysing training-related content in reports and monitoring the display of REI leadership.	statistics, REI leadership framework

Table 7: BEYOND Tools for evaluating training effectiveness for academics and experts

* The Self-Reflection Form link enables the facilitator to make a copy of the form, which they can then edit, and the data will accumulate on the facilitator’s cloud service (Google or Microsoft).

** Analysis instruments are described in WP4.2, later available at the Embassy’s website.

For instance, to measure participants’ reactions during or right after the training, *Self-Reflection Form* can be used. In addition, if learners worked in groups so their group discussions can be monitored, and if they provided a group-report or pre- and post-texts, the learning process can be evaluated based on the SOLO taxonomy to measure the levels of understanding. Moreover, if possible, a couple of months after the training an additional case study could be given to the same learners, and the content of their analysis could again be evaluated with the SOLO taxonomy. Analysing vignettes and participating in national REI surveys would be relevant for this target group. This kind of effectiveness measure would give a possibility to triangulate the measurement in different time points.

An example for implementation can be found here: [ENERI CR material example.pptx](#)

5. Implementation of the training materials - Example

As a facilitator it is a good idea to familiarise oneself with the pedagogical aspects of effective training – using cases, collaboration, scaffolding. A good training starts with careful planning,

where the learning outcomes, activities and assessment are aligned – various taxonomies can be used to achieve this. (please see chapters 2, 3 and 4 for more details).

One example of how to use a training resource from one of the EU-funded projects implementing ideas of case-based, collaborative and scaffolded learning presented in this Trainer Guide is presented below. The template is structured according to the following contents:

1. Title page indicating the activity
2. Learning objectives/outcomes
3. Topics related to the content
4. Key issues to focus on
5. Instruction page for activity
6. Case
7. Questions to guide ethical analysis
8. Further ideas/insights/feedback to learners
9. Assessment of learning and suggestion for how to use this information for evaluating the effectiveness of training

This structure is implementable with all contents in the ENERI Classroom, and provides a case-based, collaborative and scaffolded approach to adaptation and use of the wide materials and activities presented in the ENERI Classroom.

The target group of the training is supervisors and mentors. There are various training materials (see chapter 4) for this target group, we picked the ENERI Classroom material about mentoring for stronger cultures of integrity and made the website (<https://classroom.eneri.eu/mentoring>) content into slides.

The learning outcomes align with the ‘understanding’ and ‘application’ levels of the Bloom taxonomy; ‘multistructural’ level of the SOLO taxonomy, and include ‘foundational knowledge’, ‘application’, ‘integration’ and ‘human dimension’ aspects of the Fink’s taxonomy.

Learning outcomes of this training session:

- **Understanding** what the **elements** contributing to a culture of integrity in research communities are;
- **Being aware** of both the implicit and explicit ways in which **supervisors and mentors influence** the learning processes of their supervisees/mentees and others working in the research community
- **Understanding** the **role** of and **possessing a command of practices** that supervisors and mentors employ in establishing a culture of integrity

Supervisors and mentors have a chance to collaboratively discuss various topics connected with research ethics and integrity. They can provide peer support but also facilitator support can be integrated (see scaffolding techniques).

Seniors in the research community have a responsibility to mentor and supervise on research ethics and integrity

- **Discuss the following aspects:**

1. Integration to academic community
2. Awareness of and access to guidelines
3. Acceptance of guidelines
4. Positive role-models for newcomers and less experienced colleagues
5. Alignment of guidelines with local practices
6. Transparency of practices
7. Climate conducive of discussion
8. A shared mission that reaches beyond individual gain
9. Respect of others

Read more at: <https://classroom.eneri.eu/mentoring>

Then the key issues can be highlighted:

Key Issues

Infrastructure

Practices based on procedures and routines

REI training

Available, regular, different target groups

Facilitators

Who should facilitate REI trainings?

Support by leaders

Commitment to supporting the culture of integrity

Dealing with problems

Proactive approach, attention to REI topics, maintaining reputation

After that the case-based approach is utilized: the participants work in teams of 3-4 and are asked to do the following tasks: instructions, reading the case and conducting ethical analysis and contemplating additional topics:

• **Practical task - analysing a case (in groups)**

- Please read the situation described by a doctoral student;
- Analyse the case following the ethical analysis steps (Mustajoki & Mustajoki, 2017);
- Think about additional questions.

Source: Lofström, E. & Pyhältö, K. (2014) Ethical Issues in Doctoral Supervision - The perspectives of PhD students in the Natural and Behavioural Sciences. *Ethics & Behavior*, 24(3), 195-214.

A doctoral student says:

I do not understand the game. I feel like there is something I should figure out about how academia works. I cannot even trust my own supervisor. My supervisor has presented my ideas at a conference. The supervisor was in charge of organizing this paper session. I gave my supervisor access to the paper I had been working on because I wanted her to know what I planned to talk about. I was supposed to be the first presenter. But then my supervisor changed the order so that I was to present second after my supervisor. I was in for a real surprise! My supervisor gave her talk first and it turned out to be exactly my presentation! When my turn came, I did not know what to say as my supervisor had basically presented my paper already! I was so embarrassed, because it looked like I had plagiarized my supervisor, even though it was the other way around. I tried to say things differently and bring different points to my talk, but I must have looked like a thief. How can you do something like that to another person?! It feels so wrong, but I think there is something about these hierarchies that I haven't figured out yet, because if it really was wrong, how could you do something like that and get away with it? So maybe I am wrong, and I just don't understand it? I feel so confused.

Which ethical issues do you notice?

Are any ethical principles at stake?

Who are the stakeholders in this case?

What are the rights and responsibilities of the stakeholders?

What are possible courses of action?

What could be possible implications of those solutions?

Think also about:

- What does the situation tell you about the culture of the research group?
- Who could have intervened in the situation? How?
- Is there anything that members on institutional ethics/integrity boards can do in terms of preventing such situations?

See possible answers under 'Case studies' at <https://classroom.eneri.eu/mentoring>

Support material and additional reading can be provided as scaffolding.

Evaluating the effectiveness of training.

- As evaluation of the learning outcomes the groups of learners can be asked to write a group report with the case analysis.
 - Ask participants to fill the Self-Reflection Form: <https://forms.office.com/e/qHhQDQw5mK>
- OR the QR code:

- Participants can be asked to submit another ethical analysis of a case (similar to the one done during the training) a few months later to indicate the retention and implementation of the learned competencies.

As evaluation of the learning outcomes the groups of learners can be asked to write a group report with the case analysis. To analyse the level of understanding the following framework can be used:

SOLO TAXONOMY EXPLANATION AND ADAPTATION FOR THE REI TRAINING CONTEXT

(Tammeleht et al., 2019)

SOLO TAXONOMY LEVEL	CODING/INTERPRETATION DESCRIPTION
 EXTENDED ABSTRACT	<small>(Biggs, 1999; Biggs & Tang, 2007; Lofstrom, 2012; Tammeleht et al., 2019)</small> The learner goes beyond conceptualizing the present issue making steps towards relating the ethical issues to applications beyond the present case. Displaying the ability to theorise, generate, generalise, hypothesise, create or reflect.
 RELATIONAL	The learner displays an ability to address the most relevant ethical issues and provide explanations pointing out interrelations and providing examples demonstrating own reasoning.
 MULTISTRUCTURAL	The learner demonstrates that concepts had been understood appropriately, but struggles to make connections between them and to draw conclusions based on interrelations. Knowledge-telling approach, no structuring.
 UNISTRUCTURAL	The learner identifies one relevant aspect displaying some familiarity with relevant concepts, but failing to address some more pertinent dimensions of the case.
 PRE-STRUCTURAL	The learner fails to identify a relevant ethical perspective or does not approach it in a meaningful way, repeating the words in the case without displaying evidence of own processing.

In addition to the facilitator evaluation, learner’s self-reflection form (SRF) can be used: click on the [link](#) to make a copy of the form for the training. The SRF link and QR code examples in the slide take the learners to an example form that is not editable.

Moreover, participants can be asked to submit another ethical analysis of a case (similar to the one done during the training) a few months later to indicate the retention and implementation of the learned competencies. The SOLO taxonomy can again be used to evaluate the level of understanding and make the results of group-work, self-reflection and the retention check comparable and provide a holistic picture of the learning outcomes, effectiveness of the training can be concluded based on those results.

Further examples can be found by following the links provided below:

- [Plagiarism workshop for bachelor and master students](#)
- [Ethics review in non-medical research for ECRs](#)
- [Authorship for ECRs](#)

- [Whistleblowing for ECRs](#)
- [Training material for supervisor and mentors](#)

Trainers can also use a [template](#) to design their own implementation of the ENERI Classroom using the same structured approach as the above examples.

6. Conclusions

The Trainer Guide serves as a comprehensive resource for research ethics and integrity trainers. The training materials presented in this guide can be used in a variety of ways. We encourage considering the activities and materials through the learning goals that the training is intended to support. Taxonomies provide a tool for trainers to consider what are the aims of the teaching and how to ensure that learning is best facilitated. The Trainer Guide provides a structured approach to planning training sessions that are tailored to specific learning objectives. The guide presents a variety of teaching methods that allow teachers to choose the most appropriate approach depending on the target group and objectives. By combining these methods, teachers can increase the effectiveness of their training and ensure maximum participant engagement and understanding. In addition, the guide emphasizes the importance of using the training materials described in section 4. These resources are designed to complement teaching methods and provide teachers with the necessary tools to deliver engaging and informative sessions.

An overarching aim of the BEYOND Trainer Guide is to build on existing educational resources developed through EU-funded initiatives. The guide aims to improve the effective use of educational materials, contributing to a more informed and ethically responsible research community.

7. Appendices

7.1 Appendix 1: Training materials according to project and teaching/learning activity

In the following we first introduce a collection of trainings developed by EU funded initiatives and then we will present a set of topics and indicate which trainings focus on these topics and for which target audience. We recommend that trainers and teachers define the needs and skill level of the group to be trained before selecting the material to be used. This is due to the fact that the career stage often does not reflect the level of skills and competences in terms of research ethics and integrity. Some of the training materials (i.e. materials focussing on open science and AI), are not categorised by career level as they apply to all. The following training material can be used within and/or outside the academic environment. The materials presented have been developed by EU-funded initiatives namely: PRINTEGER, ENERI, RID-SSISS, EnTIRE, VIRT2UE, Path2Integrity, INTEGRITY, BRIDGE and ROSiE.

Introduction to the initiatives

PRINTEGER

[PRINTEGER](#) project, aims to strengthen research integrity by fostering a culture where integrity is integral to excellent research, beyond just external regulation. The project seeks to improve integrity governance by focusing on researchers' everyday practices within a complex research environment

PATH2INTEGRITY

The [Path2Integrity](#) project introduces educators to innovative teaching methods that will take topics in Research Integrity and Ethics. The project provides introductory videos and information on the teaching methodology used, discussing research integrity and its significance.

INTEGRITY

The goal of [INTEGRITY](#) is to empower students and early career researchers. Rather than focusing on compliance, the project's first approach is to develop the capacity of participants to identify, consider, and address integrity concerns in research procedures.

ENERI Classroom

[ENERI Classroom](#) contains training material exploring research ethics and integrity issues focusing on academics, and research ethics and integrity experts. The research integrity advisory boards, committees handling allegations or working with research integrity policy development, research integrity officers and advisors, research integrity ombudspersons (RIOs), research ethics committees including their members and their secretariats (RECs), and experts and officers in EU-bodies are the main target groups of the training materials and curricula tool.

VIRT2UE

[The VIRT2UE Train the Trainer program](#) is designed for researchers and educators across various disciplines who wish to become Research Integrity trainers. It adopts a virtue-based approach, encouraging participants to reflect on their own perspectives and understanding of research integrity. The program emphasizes personal case reflection and practical experiences, aiming to create a strong link between theoretical knowledge and real-world application.

RID-SSISS

[The RID-SSISS](#) training aims to help beginner and more experienced researchers develop their research ethics competencies in HE institutions. A CSCL (Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning) ethics resource was designed that utilised cases, collaboration, and structural scaffolding (see Table 1 for an overview).

EnTIRE

EnTIRE is the project behind [The Embassy of Good Science](#) a Wiki based community driven platform on research ethics and integrity which provides resources such as guidelines, cases and training material for and by researchers and research taskholders who want to support good science.

BRIDGE

The Bridging Integrity in Higher Education, Business, and Society ([BRIDGE](#)) project aimed at connecting integrity practices across academia, research, business, and society. BRIDGE targets early-career researchers (master's and PhD students) and their supervisors, with the first step focused on analyzing integrity practices across these fields. The project will develop checklists, open educational resources (including gamified tools), and training to bridge gaps between academic and research integrity.

ROSiE

The [ROSiE](#) training materials will be aimed at the following groups of trainees: (i) students, (ii) early career researchers, (iii) experienced researchers, and (iv) citizen scientists. The ROSiE consortium aims to develop a didactic framework which is learner-centred; based on interests, backgrounds, and learning styles of trainees; and ensures active and collaborative involvement in the learning process.

[Training material](#)

Introducing research ethics and integrity

PRINTEGER

TARGET audience: Bachelors and masters students and Doctoral students and early career researchers

The [Upright training](#) developed by the [PRINTEGER](#) projects provides the opportunity to have an overview of common research integrity issues in the academia. The training programme has been developed with the aim of raising awareness among “newcomers” to RI and RE. Besides providing knowledge and information on the topic, the training programme contributes to the development of the moral character of researchers by encouraging reflection on specific dilemmas and cases.

With its [introductory module](#), it aims to give students a first look at why research integrity matters. This module is based on the film *On Being A Scientist*, produced by the Leiden University. This provides a rough overview of the subject and can be found here: [On Being A Scientist](#). The film *On*

Being A Scientist can be split up into nine episodes. Each episode focuses on a specific topic. The movie can be also found [here](#).

VIRTUE

TARGET audience: Bachelor and master students, doctoral students and early career researchers

The e-learning modules produced by the [VIRT²UE](#) project represent an introduction to relevant topics in research integrity. These modules, which foster self-learning introduce [research integrity](#), [virtue ethics relevant for RI and](#) virtue ethics under current research conditions. Moreover, the training has developed a series of [videos](#) and [reading material](#) introducing specific concepts and themes relevant to the field and practice of research integrity, such as ethical decision making in research and moral disengagement in research.

PATH2INTEGRITY

Target audience: Bachelor and master students, doctoral students and early career researchers

The [Path2Integrity](#) project introduces educators to innovative teaching methods that will take topics in Research Integrity and Ethics. The project provides introductory videos and information on the teaching methodology used, discussing research integrity and its significance. The easy to use and innovative materials can be found in the [Path2Integrity Training Programme](#) section.

[Exploring modules on research ethics and integrity topics](#)

PRINTEGER

Target audience: Bachelor and master students, doctoral students and early career researchers

Besides the introductory module, the PRINTEGER Upright training provides [modules](#) focusing specific RE and/or RI issues. These modules address topics in relation the research misconduct, questionable research practices and more research ethics-related topics. Depending on the complexity of the topic, these modules can be used for students and academics with different levels of RE/RI-related competencies.

RID-SSiSS

Target audience: Bachelor and master students, doctoral students and early career researchers

The RID-SSISS training aims to help beginner and more experienced researchers develop their research ethics competencies in HE institutions. A CSCL (Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning) ethics resource was designed that utilised cases, collaboration, and structural scaffolding. This resource provides learners with opportunities to gradually develop research ethics competencies, guiding them through three levels. The [Foundation level](#) focuses on developing (but also helping learners to recall) central concepts of RE/RI, primarily suitable for bachelor's, master's, and doctoral students but also usable with academic staff and researchers. During the Foundation level training, participants learn to guide their own REI practices and behaviour. The RID-SSISS training also provides resources for ECRs and junior academics. This material aims to develop RE/RI competencies by supporting ethical analysis competencies as a step towards increased agency in research ethics and integrity. Ethical analysis involves the following steps: identify ethical issues by determining which ethical principle might be at stake; and utilise the ethical analysis steps to provide solutions to ethical dilemmas. In addition to the foundational level, the project developed training materials for ECRs and junior academics ([advanced level](#)).

BRIDGE

Target audience: Bachelor and master students, doctoral students and early career researchers

The [BRIDGE project](#) provides [training modules](#) and [vignettes](#) that can be inserted into research ethics and integrity courses.

INTEGRITY

Target audience: secondary school students, doctoral students and early career researchers, senior academic and RE/RI experts

Empowering researchers to behave responsibly in research is at the heart of the [INTEGRITY](#) course and each individual module. For this purpose several modules each addressing a different research integrity research ethics topic have been developed. These are specifically designed for 4 different target audiences: 1) [high school students](#); 2) [undergraduate students](#); [PhD students and](#) 4) [researchers and supervisors](#). The training materials are presented alongside a [Teacher Guide](#).

Learning cards

PATH2INTEGRITY

Target audience: Secondary school students, bachelor and master students, doctoral students and early career researchers

Path 2 integrity developed a series of [learning cards](#) focusing on students in high schools ([Path2Integrity learning cards S](#)) on bachelor students, ([Path2Integrity learning cards M](#)) alongside a dedicated handbook and doctoral students ([Path2Integrity learning cards Y](#)). Each set of learning cards comes with a [handbook for educators](#) ([S-Series handbook](#), [M-Series handbook](#), [Y-Series handbook](#))

Research ethics and integrity games

INTEGRITY

Target audience: Secondary school students, bachelor and master students

The project developed the “Integrity games” a specific training tool for [undergraduate students and provides participants with interactive training materials about research integrity dilemmas.](#)

BRIDGE

Target audience: Bachelors and masters

The training games developed by the [BRIDGE project](#) use the “gamification” approach as a learning approach to raise awareness and provide very basic knowledge on RI, focusing on undergraduates and graduates. The aim of these training is to promote knowledge and awareness on the topics of research ethics and integrity in undergraduates. Online games, board games, role-play games and scenarios game can be found [here](#).

Case studies

PRINTEGER

Target audience: Doctoral students and early career researchers and Senior researchers and RERI experts

The [Upright training](#) gives the opportunity to reflect on several dilemmas from the “[Dilemma Game. Professionalism and Integrity in Research](#)”. Specifically, the Upright training proposes the following dilemmas: [With a little help](#), [Mutual favours](#), [Sharing data](#), [So close](#), [Different results](#), [Put your supervisor first](#), [Flexible scope](#), [Outliers](#), and [Invalid data](#).

VIRT2UE

Target audience: Master and bachelor students, doctoral students and early career researchers

The developed by the <http://virt/> project presents a modified version of the developed by Erasmus University Rotterdam. This exercise supports participants in identifying research integrity principles, virtues and questionable research practices in a hypothetical case. It provides a framework to consider, choose and defend alternative courses of action regarding realistic research integrity dilemmas.

ENTIRE

Target audience: Doctoral students and early career researchers, Senior researchers and RERI experts

The EnTIRE project created eight scenarios on The [Embassy of Science](#), each of which presented a fictitious story along with eight distinct themes. The purpose of each of the eight scenarios is to provide RECs, research administrators, researchers, and researchers with the opportunity to concentrate their attention on the fundamental ideas and research settings that support both local regulations and practices and effective research practices. The scenarios developed are the following: [Research Procedures and Research Integrity](#); [Collaborative Working Between Academia and Industry](#); [Data Practices, Data Management and FAIR Principles](#); [Publication, Dissemination and Research Integrity](#); [Research Environments and Research Integrity](#); [Reviewing, Evaluating,](#)

[Editing and Research Integrity](#); [Training, Supervision and Mentoring with Integrity](#); [Safeguards, Data-sharing and the Disclosure of Sensitive Results](#).

ENERI

Target audience: Senior researchers and RERI experts

The case studies developed by ENERI address themes that [research integrity and research ethics experts deal with as well as comprehensive and overlapping issues](#) involving both integrity and ethics related considerations. These include: good scientific practice, questionable research practices, research misconduct, responsible authorship, peer review, and whistleblowing, ethics review, the protection of human rights, the safety of clinical trials, informed consent procedures, research with participants unable to consent, and the protection of animals, data management and data protection, open data sharing, open access, transparency, fairness, reliability and credibility, and conflicts of interest. While RECs and RIOs are key actors in facilitating research ethics and integrity, there may be countries that lack infrastructure as well as training opportunities for actors in related key positions. A specific section focusing on the [development of proper infrastructure](#) is also present.

Virtue-ethics based training

VIRT2UE

Target audience: Master and bachelor students, doctoral students and early career researchers, senior researchers and RERI experts

The [VIRT²UE](#) project designed a training programme with a virtue ethics approach to Ethics and Research Integrity. In particular, the VIRT2UE training supports participants in developing moral character through reflecting on real-world research integrity (RI) challenges, strengthening professional ethics by reflecting on the profession's goals, and encouraging cultivation of virtues by linking scientific virtues to advancing knowledge and by fostering the cultivation of an ethos of science by recognizing and internalizing these virtues and their connection to common guiding principles. The project developed specific modules and training materials on the relevance of virtue

ethics to research integrity: The modules address: e a) [introduction of virtue ethics to research integrity](#) and b) [virtue ethics under current research conditions](#), Moreover, the training provides introductory [readings](#) and [videos](#) to specific concepts and themes and specific topic pages introducing [epistemic virtues](#) and [virtues in research integrity](#)

In addition to the online self-learning material the VIRT2UE training also includes five participatory exercises fostering group learning on real cases and experiences brought up by the participants themselves: [Debate and Dialogue](#), [Virtues and Norms](#), [The Middle Position](#), the and the [Self-Declaration Approach](#).

Training materials for supervision and mentorship practices

INTEGRITY

Target audience: doctoral students and early career researches, senior researchers and RERI experts

The [INTEGRITY](#) project developed training materials for supervisors to encourage reflection on the ethical challenges that supervision brings about. These consist in an online course (SPOC) and a *diner pensant* script.

RID-SSISS

Target audience: doctoral students and early career researches, senior researchers and RERI experts

The RID-SSISS training for academics aims to develop leadership competencies by combining senior academics' extant knowledge base with RE/RI and new leadership competencies. In addition to the foundational level, and the advanced level, the RID-SSISS project developed a training for supervisors and leaders ([leadership level](#)).

VIRT2UE

Target audience: doctoral students and early career researches, senior researchers and RERI experts

The [VIRT²UE](#) project developed a training module introducing [supervision and mentorship practices](#). This module highlights the relevance of supervision, mentoring, and role-modelling in research environments and provides definitions of roles and their corresponding responsibilities.

BRIDGE

Target audience: doctoral students and early career researches, senior researchers and RERI experts

The [BRIDGE project](#) developed a specific [module for supervisors](#).

training materials for training research integrity and ethics trainers

VIRT2UE

Target audience: doctoral students and early career researches, senior researchers and RERI experts

The [VIRT²UE](#) project designed a Train-the-Trainer training programme with a virtue ethics approach to Ethics and Research Integrity. The VIRT2UE training programme takes a blended learning approach and consists of four components: 1) online course (consisting of 4 modules, addressing [introduction to research integrity](#), [introduction of virtue ethics to research integrity](#), [virtue ethics under current research conditions](#) and [supervision and mentorship practices](#), [preparatory readings](#) and [preparatory watching](#); 2) two consecutive participatory session (during which participants experience five participatory exercises) : [Debate and Dialogue](#), [Virtues and Norms](#), [The Middle Position](#), the [Modified Dilemma Game](#), and the [Self-Declaration Approach](#); 3) [interim practice](#) work (during which trainers in training go back to their institution practice with the exercises and reflect on their own teaching practices by means of guided self-reflection) and 4) follow up participatory [group/reflection section](#), in which future trainers can reflect on the experience, learn about teaching strategies and reflect on their own teaching style and audience. The train-the-trainer program developed precise instructions for trainers on how to prepare, organize and facilitate the section. These instructions can be found by clicking on the [trainer tab](#) on the training webpage.

Training materials on open science

ROSiE

Target audience: not specified

By imparting the essential knowledge and cultivating particular skills and attitudes, the [ROSiE](#) Training Materials for Responsible Open Science aim to teach researchers how to perform open science responsibly and prevent research misconduct within the framework of open science.

Utilizing online training resources is another way to put blended learning into practice. This method mixes traditional in-person instruction with the usage of the internet to let students create their own learning experiences. Trainees can gain from direction and engagement with a trainer while having access to flexible and interactive training options outside of the classroom by combining in-person and online training methods. The 'conventional' learning resources produced by the ROSiE project (refer to the [ROSiE Knowledge Hub](#)) can be utilized in conjunction with the online training resources for self-directed learning developed by ROSiE to facilitate blended learning in the classroom.

Training materials on responsible open science can be found for the fields of [Social Sciences](#), [Natural Sciences](#), [Humanities](#), [Health and Life Sciences](#) and [Citizen Science](#). In addition, the ROSiE project created a [collection of case studies](#) that can be use in the traditional and/or online ROSiE training.

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS

Six different modules on responsible open science can be found [here](#), on the Embassy of Good Science and [ENERI](#) platforms. [Open Science Learning Gate](#) developed by [NERQ](#) offers the possibility to align trainings with the principles of the research community. To enhance the quality of open science practices, the 'Open Science Learning Gate' seeks to unite the research community while aligning and standardizing both a) customized and b) high-quality OS training programs.

As artificial intelligence (AI) becomes increasingly integrated into our lives and work, it is important to ensure that its development and use is both ethical and responsible. This guide is designed to help educators educate individuals and organizations about the principles and practices of responsible AI. With this section we want to help trainers to convey the importance of fairness, transparency and ethical considerations in AI systems, fostering a deeper understanding and commitment to responsible AI among their participants. Although training materials focusing on AI are still in development, we hope to give trainers insight on possible material to be used. There are different ways of using AI, not only to generate text, but also to work with your own material (proofreading, changing style, transcription). Researchers should be transparent about how they have used AI tools, as they would be about any other tools and methods. The most important requirement for any researcher is to CHECK the material generated by AI, for example in a systematic review.

Most of the resources available are made by recommendations and guidelines on the use of responsible AI. Published by the European Commission, the [Living Guidelines on the Responsible Use of Generative AI in Research](#) provides recommendations for researchers, research institutions and funding organizations. [ENAI](#) developed [a practical guide for students](#) (see also [here](#)) on the use of generative AI. [UKRIO](#) provides a full list of resources on [the use of AI in research](#).

Trainers should also consider the implication in case learners use AI to do the tasks created as part of different programs. We provide one example of what the outcome could be at the end of the guide (Appendix 7.2).

7.2 Appendix 2: Potential implications of AI to REI training

Trainers should also consider the implication in case learners use AI to do the tasks created as part of different programs. We provide one example here of what the outcome could be. When comparing the response provided by the AI and a human, the main thing to consider is that AI does not say which guidelines they rely on. The responses also remain on a relatively limited level of understanding – even if all the facts are there, the explanations rarely reach higher than e.g. multistructural level in the SOLO taxonomy. In addition, see the wider research community or

secondary stakeholders is not common in responses provided by AI. Moreover, there is limited evidence of reflection, feelings or potential change in attitudes. Of course, it still takes a competent trainer to evaluate (by perhaps combining both written and oral responses) if the learner was just using AI to complete the tasks in the training or actually engaged with the material.

An Advanced level case was inserted into <https://huggingface.co/chat/> and ethical analysis of the case was requested (questions based on Mustajoki and Mustajoki, 2017; RID-SSISS training material) (24.08.2024):

*Your research team is doing research involving preschool children. Part of your data collection scheme is to video record some planned activities during a regular day at the school. You have asked the children's parents for informed consent. Slightly over half of the parents have consented, and you feel pretty good about your upcoming data collection. On the day of the activities and recording the children whose parents had not consented to their child participating in research had to be taken to another room for the duration of the data collection. You have planned that it like this because, it will be easier to set up the cameras and to manage the data if you have only those children in the room for whom the parents have given their consent. As you then, with the help of a preschool teacher, guide the remaining children out of the room, they begin to scream and some start to cry. They feel that they are being punished for something and that they will miss out on a fun activity that the others will do. **Which ethical principles may be present in this case? Who are the stakeholders? Why them? What are the responsibilities and rights of the stakeholders? What are the possible courses of action? What are their implications?***

Here is the response from the AI:

This case raises several ethical concerns, primarily related to the rights and welfare of the preschool children. Here's a breakdown of the ethical principles, stakeholders, responsibilities, rights, and possible courses of action:

Ethical Principles:

Respect for persons: The children who were removed from the room may feel punished, excluded, or stigmatized, which could harm their self-esteem and dignity.

Beneficence: The researchers have a responsibility to ensure the well-being and safety of all children involved, including those whose parents did not provide consent.

Non-maleficence: The removal of some children from the room may cause them emotional distress, which could be considered a harm.

Autonomy: The children who were removed from the room may not have had a choice in the matter, and their parents' decision not to provide consent may not have been fully explained to them.

Stakeholders:

Children: The preschool children who are participating in the research, including those whose parents provided consent and those who did not.

Parents: The parents who provided consent for their children to participate in the research, as well as those who did not.

Researchers: The research team, including the principal investigator and any assistants.

Preschool teachers: The teachers who are responsible for the children's care and education during the research activity.

Responsibilities and Rights:

Children: The right to be treated with respect, dignity, and care. The researchers and preschool teachers have a responsibility to ensure their well-being and safety.

Parents: The right to make informed decisions about their child's participation in research. The researchers have a responsibility to provide clear information about the research and obtain informed consent.

Researchers: The responsibility to conduct research in an ethical manner, ensuring the well-being and safety of all participants. They also have a responsibility to respect the autonomy of parents and children.

Preschool teachers: The responsibility to care for and educate the children, as well as to support the researchers in conducting the research in an ethical manner.

Possible Courses of Action:

Modify the research design: Consider alternative methods that do not require separating children based on consent, such as using a different data collection method or involving all children in a way that does not require consent.

Provide alternative activities: Offer alternative activities for the children who were removed from the room, to minimize feelings of exclusion and ensure their well-being.

Improve communication: Ensure that parents and children understand the research and the reasons for separating the children. Provide clear information about the research and the benefits and risks of participation.

Reconsider the consent process: Reflect on the consent process and consider whether it was adequate. Consider obtaining consent from parents in a way that is more inclusive and respectful of their autonomy.

Implications:

Modified research design: May require significant changes to the research plan, potentially affecting the validity and reliability of the data.

Alternative activities: May require additional resources and planning, but could help minimize harm to the children who were removed from the room.

Improved communication: May help build trust with parents and children, but may not fully address the ethical concerns.

Reconsidering the consent process: May require a re-evaluation of the research plan and the consent process, potentially leading to changes in the way consent is obtained in the future.

Ultimately, the researchers should prioritize the well-being and safety of all children involved and consider alternative approaches that minimize harm and respect the autonomy of parents and children.

Possible answers provided by a human respondent:

Ethical issues that could emerge in this case: underage children, parental consent, procedure of getting the consent, considering the wishes of the child, organising data collection, cooperation with

the (pre)school, which is more harmful for the child - being recorded (for the research purposes) or being upset about the procedure of fulfilling the parent's demands.

Ethical principles in this case:

respect for autonomy - in this case there is a conflict between the autonomy of the child and the autonomy of the parent - for the researchers there is no simple answer. The procedure of informing should be altered to prevent these situations from happening in the future.

doing no harm (non-maleficence) - in this case the researchers' only chance of not harming the children whose parents had not given their consent would have been not proceeding with data collection, but in that case they would be harming the research/society/greater good.

benefiting others (beneficence) - the research is probably important to the society, but it is not right to harm anyone to benefit others.

being just (justice) - the researchers must be fair towards the children, their parents, the school, the society - if their rights get into a conflict of interest, new means of data collection must be found.

being faithful (fidelity) - researchers must respect the wishes of the parents, but also children.

Who are the stakeholders? Why them? What are the responsibilities and rights of the stakeholders?

Researchers - the team of researchers need data for their research, they have planned their activities and data management, they have the support from their leader and institution, they need the research to bring new knowledge into the society and also promote their own careers.

Children - research may often include children, they will also benefit from the research. By law, underage children (there are some differences of age in different countries) need a parental consent to be part of the research. At the same time, UN Article 12 states that the child's opinion must be asked and considered (depending on their development). If the parent's and child's opinions contradict, the researchers cannot decide what to do, the best option might be to quit data collection and find new measures, and plan the informing procedure better.

Parents - are responsible for their children, have the right to decide for their underage children, must consider the well-being of their children. Parents should be aware of the implication of their

decision - whether their decision may harm the child (mentally), whether they are hindering the improvements in the society. Parent should seek for more information to consider all the alternatives.

(Pre)School - if the school allows the researchers conduct data collection in their institution, then the school leader should also be informed and evaluate the situation - either make suggestions on how better organise data collection and what the benefit is to the children/school.

Research institution - provide guidance, training to the researchers on how to better organise data collection, especially involving people/children. Maybe an ethics review is necessary or advice from the ethics committee.

Society - needs research for improvements, should encourage researchers conduct research to develop better policies. It is important to spread knowledge that all citizens can contribute to improvements by participating in surveys.

What are the possible courses of action? What are their implications? - this event is done and it was harmful to the children - it would have been better if the researchers had stopped the data collection procedure once they learned that some children cannot participate in video recording. Maybe more time should have been spent on informing parents. In the future the research teams should plan more time (e.g. in the data management plan) on informing and getting the consent - organising an information seminar for the parents, encouraging questions and asking also the children, giving families more time to make the decision, inventing new ways to organise recordings. Parents should also give it more thought - how can they contribute to research and society, maybe they could read some newspaper articles about how research is conducted and what happens to the collected data. Research institution should organise trainings and guidelines on data management, collection and protection.

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5.2 Research ethics and integrity leadership training

SUPERVISORS'

RESEARCH ETHICS AND INTEGRITY (REI) LEADERSHIP TRAINING

1 Get to know the REI LEADERSHIP framework. Then take the role of this kind of leader and do the following tasks.

Focusing on researchers' needs

- Consider people's needs – managing pressures and stress
- Reach out to the others' needs – what do they need to become successful in their endeavours? Do they know that guidelines and help is available?
- Contribute to people's personal development by asking: 'do those served grow as persons, do they become healthier, wiser, more autonomous, more likely to serve others?'
- Be concerned with people themselves by displaying empathy and connection with people's personal life

Developing the community

- Participate in training yourself and encourage others to participate in them; engage the research community to make common values and beliefs apparent.
- Make sure everyone knows the practices of the institution and actively participate in them – show your commitment to those practices.
- Be aware that only people who care about each other are able to disagree and give honest feedback.

Developing leadership competencies

- Balance providing support and autonomy, commit to bringing up the next generation of REI leaders.
- Develop the competence to negotiate, create and communicate vision, make human interaction a habit.
- Enact as a role-model – your own values, beliefs, behaviour, clear and honest decision-making, adherence to norms helps others align with good practices.
- Show integrity and capacity to think of others' needs before your own, serve the community, be aware of power-relations.
- If you as a leader reach your limit, you need to be able to forward the issue to a suitable person/institution (seek help).

Focusing on the open research culture

- Focus on open, supportive relationships – decrease fear and build trust – including dealing with misconduct, also allow space for making mistakes and learning from them.
- Communicate clearly the procedures and good practices.
- Make yourself available (open door/ move among your people/ participate in discussions as a partner).
- Make sure people have the confidence and courage to turn to you.

2

Read the case

You have early stage researchers in your team, who work on your project and whom you mentor. They are responsible for conducting a part of a bigger research on discriminatory practices in work places, and you want to make sure they do it in accordance to the relevant procedures and regulations. Some of the researchers will act as job seekers of ethnic background. They will call employers and monitor employers reactions to the information about their background. The employers will not know that they/their reactions are target of scientific research. The scientific contribution of the project is that it helps to reveal how racist attitudes and discriminatory practices may emerge and how common they are across certain job sectors.

3

Which ethical principles might be at stake in this case?

- autonomy
- beneficence
- doing no harm
- justice
- fidelity

4

Now discuss the following questions:

- Who are the stakeholders? Why them? What are their rights and responsibilities?
- What are the possible courses if action? What are their implications?

5

Which ethical approach does your provided solution follow?

Consequentialist

1. What would be the outcome?
2. What are the harms and benefits of the outcome?
3. How would different stakeholders feel about the harms and benefits?
4. What are the short- and long-term harms and benefits?
5. Who should make final decision?

Rule-based

1. Which codes of conduct and regulations do you need to follow?
2. What do the rules say about this situation?
3. Does your chosen course of action follow the rules and regulations?

Virtue-based

1. If you were the final decision-maker – how would you personally regard this decision?
2. Why would you make this decision?
3. How would a virtuous ("good") person act in this situation?
4. What are the values of the research community and stakeholders?

6

Which REI leadership principles and competencies would contribute to solving this case? Did you display any of them?

- People's needs
- Developing the community
- Leader's competencies
- Open culture

REMEMBER - YOU ARE THE REI LEADER!

Read more about mentoring and leadership:

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5.3 Examples of a training material for early career researchers.

Who owns the algorithm?

The results of the study, completed in collaboration between several researchers, are planned to be presented in a joint scientific publication, the co-authors of which are all researchers involved in the study. When the manuscript is ready, researcher Mars announces that from his unit, researcher Pluto wants to mark himself as the author, because the data was analysed with the algorithm he created. Researcher Pluto is not involved in the research in any other way, but in a rush, Researcher Mars asked for help from Pluto, who has the most experience with data analysis and creating algorithms. According to researcher Mars, this was only technical assistance, such as drawing up drawings or translating text, and therefore he did not consider it necessary to inform the other authors of the article about researcher Pluto's help. However, now a dispute has broken out, and researcher Mars is investigating whether other authors agree to include researcher Pluto as an author.

There is no consensus among the authors - some agree to be added as an author, others do not consider the request justified, because the algorithm cannot be the work of one scientist. To find a solution, they turn to the most experienced member of the working group, Professor Jupiter, whose opinion everyone respects.

How would you decide if you were Professor Jupiter?

- In my opinion, such a demand is completely absurd. I am turning to the head of the structural unit of researcher Pluto with the request to introduce the principles of publishing ethics and authorship criteria to the unit's researchers. (rule)
- I believe that without researcher Pluto, the corresponding publication would not have been completed, which is why his contribution was of decisive importance. I support naming him as an author because I see opportunities for future cooperation. (consequence)
- I believe that researcher Pluto has tried hard, and his mental effort deserves recognition regardless of what we think of the algorithm's affiliation. I'm in favour of adding him as an author. (care)
- I explain that not every person who helped in conducting the research is suitable as an author, but still those researchers who significantly contribute to research and are responsible for the results. I propose to thank researcher Pluto in the thanks of the article. (virtue/principle?)

Feedback points to consider in this case

- Agreement on cooperation – how to agree in transparent and unambiguous way?
- Agreement for authorship – how it is achieved?
- Current workload and enforceability of promises
- Ways of resolving disagreements

ALLEA relevant points

2.1 Research Environment

Research institutions and organisations demonstrate leadership in clear policies and procedures on good research practice and the transparent and proper handling of suspected research misconduct and violations of research integrity.

2.4 Safeguards

Researchers, research institutions, and organisations comply with relevant codes, guidelines, and regulations.

2.6 Collaborative working

All partner in research collaborations formally agree at the outset, and monitor and adapt as necessary, the expectations and standards concerning research integrity, the laws and regulations that will apply, protection of the intellectual property of collaborators, and procedures for handling conflicts and possible cases of misconduct.

2.7 Publication, Dissemination, and Authorship

- Authors formally agree on the sequence of authorship, acknowledging that authorship itself is based on: (1) a significant contribution to the design of the research, relevant data collection, its analysis, and/or interpretation; (2) drafting and/or critical reviewing of publications; (3) approval of the final publication; and (4) agreeing to be responsible for the content of the publication, unless specified otherwise in the publications.
- Authors include an “Author Contribution Statement” in the final publication, where possible, to describe each author's responsibilities and contributions.
- Authors acknowledge important work and contribute those who do not meet the criteria for authorship, including collaborators, assistants, and funders who have enabled the research.

3. Violations of Research Integrity

- Manipulating authorship or denigrating the role of other researchers in publications.

Reporting questionable behaviour? (responsible whistleblowing)

Keywords: qualitative method/research, participant observation, harm

Storm has previously worked as an expert in the field of law enforcement but has now started working as a lecturer and researcher. Storm and colleagues have formed a research group to study the daily activities of prisoners. An important part of the study is participant observation that is conducted in prison.

Storm has already visited the prison several times. One day he witnesses how one officer is clearly upset with a prisoner. As the observation day continues, Storm notices the same officer yelling at the prisoner.

What would you do if you were Storm?

1. I intervene in the situation and find out if I can ask the prisoner for details about their daily activities.

+ accountability (taking a decision in the situation and interfering)

+ respect (towards research participant)

- Honesty (using fake excuse to intervene)

2. I do not report the official, because I am concerned that by sharing my observations, I will not be allowed to continue the participatory observation and the study will fail. Supervision and training of officials is a responsibility for the agency.

+ respect (towards the institution and access to the institution)

- Respect (towards the research participant)
- accountability (not notifying about potential violation)

3. I do not report the officer because I do not want the prison officer to be punished because of me.

- + respect (towards the institution and access to the institution)
- accountability (not notifying about potential violation)
- reliability (not taking the whole research setting and the implications of this situation into consideration)

4. Although as an observer I have no obligation to report what I saw to the agency, I try to arrange a meeting with the officer's superior to share my observation.

- + accountability (taking a decision in the situation)
- + respect (towards research participant)
- + honesty (sharing the information with the institution)
- accountability (delayed interference)

Points to consider in this case

Responsibilities of researcher to various stakeholders- research participants, partner institutions, other researchers. This includes both ethical and legal duties, for example confidentiality or duty to report (misconduct). Special responsibilities might be due to vulnerable participants. Are there institutional guidelines or counsellors who could be approached for advice?

Research integrity – duties to oneself as a good professional researcher, what does that entail? Reflexivity on one's own background (in this case law enforcement) and motivation.

Management of research process: preparation for potential risks, dealing with incidental and unexpected findings or aspects of research, research ethics protocols. Are there institutional

and disciplinary guidelines? Have these issues been pre-emptively addressed, for example in the research application?

Values and principles at stake/in the balance

I intervene in the situation and find out if I can ask the prisoner for details about their daily activities.

- + accountability (taking a decision in the situation and interfering)
- + respect (towards research participant)
- Honesty (using fake excuse to intervene)

I do not report the official, because I am concerned that by sharing my observations, I will not be allowed to continue the participatory observation and the study will fail. Supervision and training of officials is a responsibility for the agency.

- + respect (towards the institution and access to the institution)
- Respect (towards the research participant)
- accountability (not notifying about potential violation)

I do not report the officer because I do not want the prison officer to be punished because of me.

- + respect (towards the institution and access to the institution)
- accountability (not notifying about potential violation)
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Although as an observer I have no obligation to report what I saw to the agency, I try to arrange a meeting with the officer's superior to share my observation.

- + accountability (taking a decision in the situation)
- + respect (towards research participant)
- + honesty (sharing the information with the institution)
- accountability (delayed interference)

A tutor in a bundle (supervision, mentoring)

Keywords: supervision, research quality, conflict resolution

Doctoral student Willow has reached the final stages of writing their thesis, with one last publication ready to be submitted to a journal. Willow is in a hurry to graduate, as the research project funding their studies is nearing its end. Willow is supervised by researcher Birch, who is also a co-author of the manuscript. However, Birch feels that their communication with Willow is increasingly strained, as Willow does not heed Birch's advice. Consequently, Birch, as both supervisor and co-author, is dissatisfied with the quality of Willow's work and believes the article is not suitable for publication in its current form. Not publishing the article would delay Willow's defense significantly, likely resulting in a period of unemployment after the project's conclusion.

What would you do instead of researcher Birch?

1. I feel that I cannot be the author of an article that is not ready for publication. Ask to be removed yourself as an author.
2. I believe that the reviewers' criticism is a good lesson for PhD student Willow. I let them send a half-baked article for peer review.

3. I rewrite the article myself in a suitable way, adding myself as the first author and PhD student Willow as the second author, and send the article for review.

4. I wouldn't do anything, because I don't want to spoil my relationship with PhD student Willow. I promise to send the article for review when the doctoral student is convinced of its readiness.

Points to consider

Good practices of supervision and mentoring, what aspects of this relationship are the responsibility of the supervisor and which the responsibility of the supervisee.

Conflict/disagreement resolution, possibility of finding a neutral advisor

Quality of research

Life after PhD

Values at stake

I feel that I cannot be the author of an article that is not ready for publication. Ask to be removed yourself as an author. (reegel)

+ honesty (being honest about the situation)

+ accountability (making a decision in this situation)

- respect (towards the PhD student as the mentor is distancing themselves from the situation).

- reliability (allowing half-baked research to continue)

2. I believe that the reviewers' criticism is a good lesson for PhD student Willow. I let them send a half-baked article for peer review. (tagajärg)

+ accountability (making a decision in this situation)

- respect (towards the PhD student as the mentor is distancing themselves from the situation).
- reliability (allowing half-baked research to continue)
- honesty (not explaining the situation and the risks to the PhD student)

3. I rewrite the article myself in a suitable way, adding myself as the first author and PhD student Willow as the second author, and send the article for review. (hoolivus)

- + accountability (taking a decision and providing a solution to this situation)
- + reliability (not allowing half-baked research to continue)
- respect (for PhD student and their ability to finish the research)
- honesty (towards PhD student and about the fact, that supervisor becomes the first author)

4. I wouldn't do anything, because I don't want to spoil my relationship with PhD student Willow. I promise to send the article for review when the doctoral student is convinced of its readiness. (voorus)

- + respect (for PhD student and their ability to finish the research)
- + reliability (working towards support for PhD student to finishing the research)
- honesty (not being honest about the situation at hand)
- accountability (not taking a decision in this situation which might leave PhD student unemployed for a while).

Reintegration of the researcher (rehabilitation)

Keywords: rehabilitation, reintegration, collaboration, trust

Olle, an established researcher with an excellent track record in science, was unexpectedly arrested and later found guilty of espionage. After serving their sentence, Olle is now seeking employment and has approached various collaborators and partners within their research field. Among those contacted is Sam, a colleague from another institution with whom Olle had previously collaborated successfully.

Olle's arrest and conviction came as a shock to colleagues. Despite the past incident, Olle is determined to reintegrate into the scientific community and continue their research career, believing that with the sentencing the punishment has been completed. Olle reaches out to Sam, hoping to leverage their previous positive working relationship to secure a new position.

What would you do if you were Sam?

1. I would hire Ollie as they have served the punishment and there is no need for additional punishment.
2. I would not hire Ollie as this would undermine the public trust in our activities.
3. I would offer Ollie activities they can perform but would not higher them as permanent member of the staff.
4. I would not hire Ollie, but since we have had previous good collaboration together, I would offer a very good letter of recommendation.

Points to consider

Rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers: on what conditions?

Trust in collaboration: how can this be rebuilt, can this be rebuilt?

Academic reputation of individuals and institutions, what affects it? Who has responsibility to protect it?

Values at stake

I would hire Ollie as they have served the crime and there is no need for additional punishment. (reegel)

- + respect (for colleague as they have served their sentence)
- + accountability (supporting the reintegration of the researcher after misconduct)
- reliability (quality of the research performed by Ollie might be questioned by the public)

I would not hire Ollie as this would undermine the public trust in our activities. (tagajärg)

- + honesty (being honest with Ollie about the reason for not hiring them)
- + reliability (quality of the research performed by Ollie might be questioned by the public)
- respect (for colleague who has served their sentence)

I would offer Ollie activities they can perform but would not higher them as permanent member of the staff. (hoolivus)

- + respect (including Ollie in scientific activities after they have served their sentence)
- reliability (quality of the research performed by Ollie might be questioned by the public)
- accountability (manoeuvring around clear position in this situation, this could be considered as manipulation)

I would not hire Ollie, but since we have had previous good collaboration together, I would offer them a very good letter of recommendation for the next possibility. (voorus)

- + reliability (quality of the research performed by Ollie might be questioned by the public)
- + honesty (being honest with Ollie about the reason for not hiring them)
- respect (for colleague who has served their sentence)
- accountability (not taking a clear position, suggesting someone else should take the position).

Colleague's accusation (integrity, conflict resolution)

Keywords: integrity, professional conduct, conflict resolution

Research fellow Bright approaches the head of the research group, Professor Smith, to complain about the behavior of their colleague, research fellow North. Bright reports that students have observed North behaving indecently and staggering around during Walpurgis Night. Bright asserts that this is not the first such incident and believes that North's behavior violates the principles of good scientific practice, undermines the integrity and reliability of the research institution, and sets a poor example for students. Bright insists that immediate action is necessary, stating that it is difficult to work with North under these circumstances and threatens to file an official complaint if no action is taken.

Professor Smith then speaks with research fellow North, who acknowledges that the events might have occurred as described by Bright but argues that such behavior does not constitute a violation of research integrity. North contends that accusing her of damaging academia is unfair and malicious. She emphasizes that her personal time is her own and that recent work-related stress has contributed to her actions.

What would you do if you were professor Smith?

1. I'd feel the conflict needs to be solved but I couldn't objectively assess the situation myself. I'd delegate the case to the head of department.
2. I'd try to mend things between the co-workers, stressing that our joint goal is to complete the research project. After that we could discuss if long-time cooperation is in the cards.
3. I'd explain to Bright that what research fellow North does in their free time is private business and has nothing to do with research integrity. I'd ask them not to submit an official complaint as that would only harm our work relationship.
4. I'd agree with research fellow Bright's critique and warn North against such behaviour – serious consequences might follow and their career at the institution might suffer.

Points to consider

Integrity and professional conduct, private and professional lives

Responsibilities of researchers and mentors

Conflict resolution

Academic reputation, of researchers and institutions

Values at stake

I'd feel the conflict needs to be solved but I couldn't objectively assess the situation myself. I'd delegate the case to the head of department. (reegel)

- + accountability (taking the situation seriously)
- + respect (taking Bright's discomfort seriously)
- accountability (delegating the decisions-making)

I'd try to mend things between the co-workers, stressing that our joint goal is to complete the research project. After that we could discuss if long-time cooperation is in the cards. (tagajärg)

- + respect (for colleagues)
- + accountability (dealing with the situation)
- accountability (long term solution will be sought later in time)

I'd explain to Bright that what research fellow North does in their free time is private business and has nothing to do with research integrity. I'd ask them not to submit an official complaint as that would only harm our work relationship. (hoolitsus)

- + respect (towards personal life)
- Accountability (not taking the situation seriously)

- respect (towards Bright's discomfort)

I'd agree with research fellow Bright's critique and warn North against such behaviour – serious consequences might follow and their career at the institution might suffer. (voorus)

- + accountability (dealing with the situation)
- + respect (taking Bright's discomfort seriously)
- respect (North's perspective is not taken into account)

Funding decision (AI in research)

Keywords: AI, funding, fairness/objectivity, grant evaluation

Marke is an expert reviewer in a funding body. In a new round of grant decisions, the reviewers are instructed to create their own ranking list of the projects. Marke has read through all the assigned projects, provided feedback and points and is now reviewing the first version of the ranking list. Marke notices that in list the first and the second project have the

same number of points and now Marke needs to decide how to rank them. When re-reading the projects, it emerges that one of the projects states their use of AI in project writing and lists all the elements AI was used for (brainstorming, structuring, editing) while the second project does not mention use of AI. The funding body has not indicated any rules about the use of AI, but they have stated that transparency as regards of using AI is a must.

How would you list the projects if you were Marke?

1. Since there are no rules listed for using AI besides transparency, I try to find another point from the assessment guide to differentiate between the projects.
2. I believe that most researchers use AI in one or another way and therefore I give extra credit to the project that is transparent in its usage.
3. Since I don't know if the second project used the AI or not, I ask the funder if they have any information on that matter and ask for advice how to proceed with the information.
4. I trust that both projects were transparent in the proposals, and therefore I think the project that did not use AI should be rewarded for that (ie not doing shortcuts).

Below are some points to consider in the discussion of the case, please also discuss where do the responsibilities for those concerns lie (eg reviewer, funding body, policy-level)?

Ethical concerns around evaluation: transparency and consistency of evaluation and decision-making process, proper documentation and good quality guidelines, fairness and objectivity in assessment, decision-making in the context of incomplete information.

Concerns around AI: the fast pace of development of AI, lack of concrete guidelines or policies, biases concerning (the use of) AI.

Values and principles at stake

Since there are no rules listed for using AI besides transparency, I try to find another point from the assessment guide to differentiate between the projects.

- + honesty (trying to find an honest way to assess equal projects)
- accountability (not taking into consideration the information provided in the application)
- respect (for the proposal being transparent about use of AI)

I believe that most researchers use AI in one or another way and therefore I give extra credit to the project that is transparent in its usage.

- + honesty (being honest in the assessment criteria)
- + accountability (taking into consideration the information provided in the application)
- + respect (towards the proposal being transparent about use of AI)
- accountability (assuming information)

Since I don't know if the second project used the AI or not, I ask the funder if they have any information on that matter and ask for advice how to proceed with the information.

- + accountability (asking for missing information)
- + respect (towards proposals, not assuming information)

- respect (towards the proposal being transparent in AI use)
- Accountability (potentially delaying the decision)

I trust that both projects were transparent in the proposals, and therefore I think the project that did not use AI should be rewarded for that (ie not doing shortcuts).

- + honesty (being honest in the criteria)
- accountability (assuming information)
- respect (towards proposal being transparent about AI use)

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